

Ethiopia's Quest to Access the Sea: An International Law Perspective

*Abebew Sisay Alemnow,
Federal Public Prosecutor,
FDRE Ministry of Justice,
Addis Ababa, Ethiopia.*

Email: abebawsisaylaw@gmail.com

This article reflects the personal views of the author, and not his employer or government.

Abstract:

Ethiopia is the most populous land locked country located in East Africa. On 23 October 2023 Ethiopian Prime Minister Abiy Ahmed announced officially to Ethiopians and the international community that Ethiopia has a legitimate right to access the Red Sea. The Prime Minister underscored that Ethiopia has legal, historical and geographical right to access the Red Sea. Further he argued that the population of over 120 million cannot be confined in a geographic prison. Ethiopia perceived its quest as existential necessity for its economic development and military security in the horn of Africa. Owing to this, Ethiopia is on an ongoing effort to realize its quest for access to the sea by crafting multi-faceted approaches. This article will examine the legality of Ethiopia's ambition to access the sea by scrutinizing relevant international laws and principles focusing on the maritime accord signed with Somaliland, Ethiopia's claims of ownership over Assab and international law of sea. Ultimately, the article recommends the ways in which Ethiopia's ongoing quest for access the sea can be realized.

Keywords: Algiers Agreement, Ethiopia, International law, Sea, Statehood, Red Sea.

1. INTRODUCTION

The quest of landlocked countries to access the sea has been and will continue to be the controversial areas of international law of sea.¹ Most recently, Ethiopia's pursuit to access the sea is a pioneering one. Ethiopia's ongoing ambition to access the Red Sea is not an accidental and sudden outburst allegation.² Rather, the agenda of Ethiopia's access to the sea is the main concern of Ethiopia's foreign policy throughout its history.³ In modern Ethiopian history access to the sea was one of the objectives of foreign policy of all regimes except the Tigray People Liberation Front (TPLF) dominated Ethiopian People Revolutionary Democratic Front (EPRDF).⁴ EPRDF didn't attempt any mechanisms to answer Ethiopia's quest for access to the sea rather than perceiving it as a commodity.⁵ Consequently, the question of Ethiopia's right to access the sea was one of the controversial issues among politicians and the government officials during Eritrean independence. Ironically, EPRDF disregarded Ethiopia's quest for access to the sea as untenable jingoistic fantasy, contending that it's motivated by "irredentist and ultra-nationalist sentiment" rather than realistic foreign policy considerations.⁶

On 23 October 2023 Abiy Ahmed made an unprecedented historical speech to the members of the parliament.⁷ In his speech he stated that Ethiopia has a legitimate right to access the Red sea based on geography, history and demography.⁸ He further stated that Ethiopia would not use force to secure its legitimate right over the Red sea.⁹ However, Ethiopia's official announcement of its allegation on the Red Sea creates trepidation on all neighboring coastal states except Kenya and Sudan since they act immediately by undermining Ethiopia's claim to access the sea. From ongoing debate among government officials in government Medias and from the repeated speech of Ethiopia Prime Minister, Ethiopia has invoked multi-faceted approaches to legitimize its ambition of access to the sea. Firstly, it signed a maritime accord with Somaliland in exchange for recognition.

¹ Shimelash Wondale, 'Ethiopia's Right to the Sea under International Law' *The Reporter* (Addis Abeba, 8 March 2025) <<https://www.thereporterethiopia.com/44075/>> accessed 13 April 2025.

² Samuel Getachew, 'Ethiopia's quest to access seaports faces headwinds, threatening regional stability' *Ajambo Africa* (15 April 2025) <<https://www.amjamboafrika.com/ethiopias-quest-to-access-seaports-faces-headwinds-threatening-regional-stability/>> accessed 17 April 2025.

³ Shimelash Wondale Dagne & Tebarek Lika Megento, 'Effects of Ethiopia's landlocked status on ties with its Neighbours' (2024)12 (1) *African Journal of Political Science* 19

⁴ Haimanot Tsegaye, 'The Red Sea Security Dynamics and Its Implication on Ethiopia's National Security' (MA Thesis, Addis Abeba University 2024)

⁵ Tezera Tazebew, 'Ethiopia's Quest for Utilizing the Port of Berbera, Somaliland, since 2010: Drivers, Processes, and Challenges' (2017) 6(1) *Journal of Ethiopian Studies* 1

⁶ Abtamu Tahir Mohammed, 'Opinion: From Lost Cause to National Agenda: Ethiopia's bold move to end landlocked isolation, secure coastal gateway' *Addis Standard* (Addis Abeba, 10 March 2025) <<https://addisstandard.com/from-lost-cause-to-national-agenda-ethiopias-bold-move-to-end-landlocked-isolation-secure-coastal-gateway/>> accessed 13 April 2025

⁷ Fana Television, 'ከጠብቃ ውኃ እስከ ባሕር ውኃ [From a Drop of Water to the Sea]' accessed from <<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8nIkFolF2Tw>> [Hear in after Fana Television]

⁸ *Ibid*

⁹ Al-Arabiya English, "Ethiopia's Abiy seeks to quell neighbors' concerns over invasion regarding sea access" accessed from <<https://english.alarabiya.net/News/world/2023/10/26/Ethiopia-s-Abiy-seeks-to-quell-neighbors-concerns-over-invasion-regarding-sea-access>>

Secondly, it asserts claims of ownership over Assab it's currently the territorial part of Eritrea. Thirdly, it asserts its legitimate right to access the sea by invoking the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS). Therefore, by examining several scholastic and technical arguments from historical and legal literatures, international laws and judicial decisions this article will attempt to examine the legality of those approaches under international law.

2. ETHIOPIA'S HISTORICAL QUEST TO ACCESS THE RED SEA: PAST TO PRESENT

Ethiopia uses the Red Sea in its long history as a major outlet to engage in diplomatic and commercial relationships with the rest of the world.¹⁰ Ethiopia's historical right on the Red Sea begins to be intricate in the medieval period of Ethiopia history, when European powers began to scramble the Horn of Africa. Firstly, the occupation of Massawa and Red sea in the 16th century by Ottoman Turks,¹¹ the colonization of Eritrea and recognizing Eritrea as the colony of Italy by Emperor Menelik had created landlocked Ethiopia in 1993.¹² Emperor Menelik did not want to rely on the port of Assab, which was under the colonial rule of Italy; instead he entered into an arrangement with France to build a rail way from the port of Djibouti to Addis Abeba to facilitate the imports and exports of Ethiopia.¹³ The Hewett Treaty, also known as the Treaty of Adwa, was signed by Ethiopia, Egypt, and Britain in 1884.¹⁴ It provided for the free transit of Ethiopian goods including firearms and mutilations through the port of Massawa.¹⁵ This agreement was a tactical one that deprived Ethiopia's sovereignty over Massawa. Britain interpreted the treaty to mean that Ethiopia had denounced its sovereignty over Massawa and impliedly allowed Italy to occupy the port.¹⁶

Secondly, the dismantlement of Ethio-Eritrea federation in 1962 is another historical occasion for the creation of landlocked Ethiopia, hence the dissolution of federation compelled Eritrean's to struggle for their external self-determination.¹⁷

¹⁰ Firehewet Asres Amte, 'The Ethio-Eritrea Rapprochement since 2018 and Ethiopia's quest for access to the Red Sea' (MA Thesis, Addis Abeba University 2024)

¹¹ Samuel Negash, 'Ethiopia's Elusive Quest for an Outlet to the Sea: The Case of the Haud-Zeila Exchange from the 1920s to the 1950s, Movements in Ethiopia' (2016) 1 Proceedings of the 18th International Conference on Ethiopian Studies 257

¹² Calchi Novati and Gian Paolo, 'Revisionism vs. Conservationism in the Horn and the Role of Ethiopia' (2016) 2 Proceedings of the 18th International Conference on Ethiopian Studies 1

¹³ Abebe Zegeye & Melakou Tegegn, 'Post War Border Dispute between Ethiopia and Eritrea: On the Brink of another War?' (2008) 24(2) Journal of Developing Societies 245

¹⁴ Workaferahu Aklilu, 'Ethiopia's Quest for Access to the Sea and Its Implications for Relations with Neighboring Littoral Countries' (MA Thesis, Addis Abeba University 2025)

¹⁵ Ibid

¹⁶ Wikipedia, 'Hewett Treaty' accessed from <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hewett_Treaty> accessed on 25 November 2025

¹⁷ Anwar Seid Suleiman, 'Imagining the Nation: Assessing the Role and Functioning of the Eritrean Assembly in the Eritrean-Ethiopian Federation (1952-1962)' (MA Thesis, Leiden University 2013)

Thirdly, abandonment of Ethiopia's legal and historical claim of ownership over former French Somaliland (Djibouti) is another historical occasion that subverts Ethiopia's sea access opportunities in the East.¹⁸ France agreed with Emperor Menelik to hand over Djibouti to Ethiopia upon its withdrawal in 1896. Emperor Haile Selassie attempted to unify Djibouti with Ethiopia.¹⁹

However, the Derg regime has officially addressed Ethiopia's renunciation of legal and historical claims of ownership over French Somaliland (Djibouti) on the summit of the African leaders in Kampala on 29 July 1975.²⁰ Finally, Recognizing Eritrea as independent sovereign state without claiming Assab and delimitation of Ethio-Eritrea boundary dispute based on colonial treaties and principle of *uti possidetis* is a major historical event which eradicates Ethiopia's historical right over the coastal area of the Red Sea. Emperor Haile Selassie had attempted several diplomatic approaches and appeals to the international community and institutions on how Ethiopia would access the sea. In February 1945, Emperor Haile Selassie submitted memoranda to the United States of America (USA) President Franklin D. Roosevelt claiming the reunification of Eritrea and gaining direct access to the Red Sea.²¹ In 1946 Ethiopia was proposed to offer Ogaden to the British in exchange for access to the sea via the port of Zeila.²²

In 1947 Emperor Haile Selassie presented a memorandum to the members of the United Nation on how Ethiopia had lost its access to the sea.²³ In his presentation he underscored that European colonization and territorial scramble of the Horn of Africa has deprived Ethiopia's right over the coastlines of the Red Sea.²⁴ Eventually, Emperor Haile Selassie became triumphant by federating Eritrea with Ethiopia in 1952.²⁵ Eritrean declaration of independence in 1993 eradicates Ethiopia's historical right on the Red Sea.²⁶ Nevertheless, Ethiopia used the port of Assab until the outbreak of border war

¹⁸ Urgessa Deressa Gutu, 'The Ethio-Djibouti Relations: Implications for Sub-Regional Integration Schemes in the Horn of Africa' (MA Thesis, Addis Ababa University 2014)

¹⁹ Awet Halefom, 'The Geopolitics of the Red Sea and Ethiopia's Foreign Policy Options: Tracing Policy Responses across the Successive Regimes (1930s-2018)' (MA Thesis, Ethiopia Civil Service University 2022)

²⁰ Fentahun Ayele, 'A Historical Investigation of Ethiopia's Claims over Djibouti' (2023) 9(1) Ethiopian Journal of Social Sciences 22

²¹ Britannica, 'The rise and reign of Haile Selassie I (1916-74)' accessed from <<https://www.britannica.com/place/Ethiopia/The-rise-and-reign-of-Haile-Selassie-I-1916-74>>

²² Galbeedi, 'Somaliland: Is Renewed Ethio-Somalia Relations Bringing The Zeila Equation Back Into Focus' (Somalia Online, 23 February 2020) <<https://www.somaliaonline.com/community/topic/164217-somaliland-is-renewed-ethio-somalia-relations-bringing-the-zeila-equation-back-into-focus/>> accessed on 21 August 2025

²³ Mohhamed Farah Hersi, 'Ethiopia's quest for Access to Red Sea and Gulf of Aden; Historical Precedents and Contemporary implications' (2024) Academic for Peace and Development 1

²⁴ Ibid

²⁵ Gizachew Asrat & Gashaw Ayferam Endaylalu, 'Ethiopia's Quest for Sovereign Sea Access: Historical and Geopolitical Contexts' (2025) 17(1) Journal of Middle Eastern Studies 149

²⁶ Seyoum Yohanns, 'Eritrea-Ethiopia Arbitration: A cure based on neither Diagnosis nor Prognosis' (2012) 6(2) Mizan Law Review 164

between two States in 1998.²⁷ EPRDF renounced Ethiopia's inherent right over the coastal area of the Red Sea by recognizing Eritrea without alleging Ethiopia's right on the Red Sea.²⁸ This is the first mistake made by EPRDF in depriving Ethiopia's right over the Red Sea. Ironically, EPRDF, made a similar miscalculation in 2000 which compromised Ethiopia's legitimate right of access to the sea. On 12 December 2000 EPRDF signed the Algiers Agreement, which affect the realization of Ethiopia's right of access to the Red Sea.

In this agreement Ethiopia agreed to delimit and demarcate boundary dispute in accordance with colonial treaties, principle of *uti possidetis juris* and applicable international law. Ethiopia and Eritrea signed two bilateral agreements to enforce the decision of the Ethio-Eritrea Boundary Commission (EEBC) to revitalize their diplomatic relationship in 2018.²⁹ Specifically, On 9 June 2018 they signed an agreement called the Joint Declaration of Peace and Friendship in Asmera.³⁰ Pursuant to this agreement, Ethiopia agreed to enforce the ruling of EEBC.³¹ Similarly, on 16 September 2018 in the presence of United Nation Secretary General Antonio Gutters, they signed Jeddah Peace Agreement that promised to implement the decision of EEBC in exchange for using Massawa and Assab ports.³² However, those agreements remained a gentleman's agreement and were never enforced.

Currently, Ethiopia is in an ongoing effort to realize its quest of access to the sea by adopting multi-dimensional approaches. There are three reasons advanced by the Revised Foreign Policy Draft Document of 2019, for Ethiopia's need to access the sea.³³ First, demographic and economic growth: Ethiopia is the most populous landlocked country and has a fast growing population and economy in the world.³⁴ Such expansion significantly heightens the demand for diversified, reliable, and cost-effective access to the sea for international trade, as reliance on a single port, Djibouti, creates a

²⁷ Tesfaye B. Takele & Tassew D. Tolcha, 'Optimal transit corridors for Ethiopia' (2021) *Journal of Transport and Supply Chain Management* 1

²⁸ Gizachew Asrat and Gashaw Ayferam, 'Ethiopia's Quest for Sea Access: Balancing between Escalation and D-Escalation' (Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia Institute of Foreign Affairs, 19 November 2024) <<https://www.ifa.gov.et/2024/11/19/ethiopias-quest-for-sea-access-balancing-between-escalation-and-d-escalation/>> accessed on 17 April 2025

²⁹ 'Full text of the Ethio-Eritrea agreement signed in Jeddah' *Addis Standard* (Addis Abeba, 18 September 2018) <<http://addisstandard.com/full-text-of-the-ethio-eritrea-agreement-signed-in-jeddah/>> accessed on 12 September 2025

³⁰ Lyons SW, 'Joint Declaration of Peace and Friendship between Eritrea and Ethiopia' (2019) 58(1) *American Society of International Law* 237

³¹ *Ibid*

³² King Faisal Center for Research and Islamic Studies, 'Red Sea Peace Initiatives: Saudi Arabia's Role in the Eritrea- Ethiopia Rapprochement' (2022) *Special Report*

³³ Shimellis Hailu, Hussein Jemma & Yonas Ashine, 'Ethiopia's Quest for Sea Access: Strategic Imperatives, Responses and Geopolitical Repercussions' (2025) 12(2) *Ethiopian Renaissance Journals of Social Sciences and the Humanities* 113

³⁴ Ebssa Wakwaya, 'The promise of regional projects for Africa's landlocked countries: Focusing on Ethiopia' (2014) 9(2) *Journal of Political Science and International Relations* 68

disproportionate economic burden and vulnerability.³⁵ Second, military and security concerns: being landlocked presents a 'national security vulnerability' and limits Ethiopia's ability to safeguard its interests, project power, and participate fully in the strategic order of the Red Sea-Gulf of Aden region, which is a vital global trade route and an arena for geopolitical competition.³⁶ Third, the quest for sea access is couched as part of Ethiopia's desire to become a regional superpower and to further regional stability and integration. It aims to return to its historical and legitimate place in the governance of the Red Sea to ensure its interests, intrinsically linked with the stability and prosperity of the region are secured.³⁷

However, some scholars, mainly the members of opposition political parties, contend that the regime of Abiy Ahmed has raised the issue of the Red Sea to maximize its legitimacy and to divert the dimension of the international community towards ongoing internal armed conflicts.³⁸ Conversely, others contend that the Abiy Ahmed administration is truly a Red Sea-access nationalist and committed to addressing Ethiopia's demands. They argue that this stance is not merely a tactic to redirect international attention away from ongoing armed conflicts, citing four justifications to support this position. firstly, the Ministry of Peace has prepared a draft document titled 'Ethiopia's National Interest; Principles and Content' which stipulates Ethiopia's right to access the Red Sea and Gulf of Aden.³⁹

Secondly, before the outbreak of ongoing internal armed conflicts, the government has drafted a foreign policy document in 2019 that recognizes Ethiopia's legitimate right of access to the Red Sea.⁴⁰ Thirdly, Ethiopia's legitimate right to access the sea is enshrined as one objective of Ethiopia's foreign policy in guiding principle of the Prosperity Party called ሞደሞር (medemer).⁴¹ Fourthly, Prime Minister Abiy Ahmed expressed Ethiopia's ambition to access the sea in his consultation with the members of

³⁵ 'Diversifying Ethiopia's port options: A strategic necessity for trade and economic growth' The Reporter (Addis Abeba, 17 February 2024) <<https://www.thereporterethiopia.com/38682/>> accessed on 25 November 2025

³⁶ 'Ethiopia's Long March to the Sea: Rekindling a Lost Maritime Destiny' FDRE Institute of Foreign Affairs (Addis Abeba, 13 November 2025) <<https://www.ifa.gov.et/2025/11/13/understanding-ethiopias-quest-to-sea-access-the-strategic-cost-of-being-landlocked/>>

³⁷ 'Demystifying Ethiopia's Rise: Growth Trajectories and Its Transition to Regional Power' FDRE Institute of Foreign Affairs (Addis Abeba, 25 May 2025) <https://www.ifa.gov.et/2025/05/25/demystifying-ethiopias-rise-growth-trajectories-and-its-transition-to-regional-power/>

³⁸ Ashenafi Endale, 'Ethiopia's quest for port access: Does it sound realistic?' The Reporter Magazine (Addis Abeba, 1 November 2023) <<https://thereportermagazines.com/2000/>> accessed on 13 April 2025

³⁹ Ashenafi Endale and Selamawit Mengesha, 'Red Sea takes center stage as Ethiopia looks to assert regional presence' The Reporter (Addis Abeba, 14 October 2023) <<https://www.thereporterethiopia.com/36980/>> accessed on 12 September 2025

⁴⁰ Tilahun Abeje Chanie, 'Understanding Ethiopia's Maritime Deal with Somaliland Through Abiy Ahmed's Foreign Policy' (2024) 3(1) International Journal of Geopolitics and Governance 110

⁴¹ Fana Television

Ethiopia's Defense Force on June 11, 2018.⁴² Accordingly, they contends that the regime of Abiy Ahmed is true Red Sea nationalist and committed to answer Ethiopia's quest to access the sea rather than using it as means to redirect the attention of local and international actors on the internal armed conflicts.

3. THE LEGALITY OF ETHIO-SOMALILAND MARITIME ACCORD UNDER INTERNATIONAL LAW

Signing maritime accord with Somaliland in exchange for recognition is the first inefficacious attempted approach to realize Ethiopia's demand of procuring adequate sea access. Ethiopia signed an erratic and controversial Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) with the internationally unrecognized Somaliland on 1 January 2024, in Addis Ababa.⁴³ Pursuance to MOU, Somaliland has agreed to lease 20 kilometers of its coastline in exchange for recognition from Ethiopia.⁴⁴ However MOU was immediately met with strong opposition from Somalia, declaring the agreement a violation of its sovereignty.⁴⁵ A former British protectorate, Somaliland gained its independence on 26 June 1960.⁴⁶

However, after five days of its independence, Somaliland and Somalia have agreed to unite and formed the Republic of Somalia.⁴⁷ Unfortunately, after the downfall of the Seid Barie military regime Somaliland declared itself as an independent sovereign state in 1991.⁴⁸ Despite this, Somalia has still regarded Somaliland as the integral part of its territory. Consequently, two divergent arguments have emerged among legal scholars. Some contend that so long as Somaliland is not recognized as a sovereign state, signing an MOU with Somaliland in exchange for recognition is against international law and the

⁴² 'Ethiopia's Quest for Sea Access' Ethiopia's Peace Observatory (12 February 2024) <<https://epo.acleddata.com/2024/02/12/ethiopias-quest-for-sea-access/>> accessed on 12 September 2025

⁴³ 'Ethiopia's gambit for a port is unsettling a volatile region: Abiy Ahmed is doing a deal for a stretch of Somaliland's coast' The Economist (London, 2 January 2024) <<https://www.economist.com/middle-east-and-africa/2024/01/02/ethiopias-gambit-for-a-port-is-unsettling-a-volatile-region>> accessed on 24 January 2025

⁴⁴ 'The Ethiopia-Somaliland Deal' International Institute for Strategic Studies <<https://www.iiss.org/publications/strategic-comments/2024/03/the-ethiopia-somaliland-deal/>> Accessed on 22 January 2025

⁴⁵ Reuters, 'Somalia rejects port deal between Ethiopia and Somaliland' accessed from <<https://www.reuters.com/world/africa/somalias-cabinet-calls-emergency-meet-ethiopia-somaliland-port-deal-2024-01-02/>> accessed on 20 April 2025

⁴⁶ Timothy A. Ridout, 'Building Peace and the State in Somalia: The Case of Somaliland' (MA Thesis, Tufts University 2011)

⁴⁷ Aaron Kreuter, 'Self-Determination, Sovereignty, and the Failure of States: Somaliland and the Case for Justified Secession' (2010) 19(2) Minnesota Journal of International Law 363

⁴⁸ Redie Berekteab, 'Self-Determination and Secessionism in Somaliland and South Sudan Challenges to Postcolonial State-Building' (2012) Discussion Paper 75

sovereignty of Somalia.⁴⁹ While some others contend that Somaliland has fulfilled all elements of statehood.⁵⁰

Therefore, recognizing Somaliland does not violate international law.⁵¹

Ethiopia and Somalia signed the Ankara Declaration under the facilitation of Turkey on 12 December 2024.⁵² In the Ankara declaration Ethiopia implicitly agreed to abandon its obsession to recognize Somaliland and to respect territorial integrity and sovereignty of Somalia, in return for obtaining sea access in Somalia.⁵³ However, some authors contend that Ethiopia's simple recognition of the territorial integrity and sovereignty of Somalia does not amount to nullification of the MOU.⁵⁴ All in all, the Ankara Declaration plays a pivotal role in deescalating geopolitical tensions in the Horn of Africa and it revitalized diplomatic relationship between two states.⁵⁵ The legality of MOU is dependent on the legal status of Somaliland under international law.⁵⁶ Hence, the legality of MOU emanated from the statehoodness of Somaliland. This paper contends that entering into a maritime accord with Somaliland in exchange for recognition is not a violation of international law, a position substantiated by the following arguments.

a. Somaliland has fulfilled the precondition of statehood

State acquires international legal personality upon the fulfillment of preconditions which are embedded in the Montevideo convention.⁵⁷ Which are permanent population, defined territory, effective government and capacity to enter into international relations.⁵⁸ The first three criteria are currently regarded as the generally accepted rule of

⁴⁹ Aljazeera English, 'Could Ethiopia and Somali go to War?' accessed from <<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=H64MmhulAC8>> accessed on 31 July 2025

⁵⁰ Marija Boise, Lekha Fernandes & others, 'A Shadow on Tomorrow's Dreams: Somaliland's Struggle for Statehood'(2016) Unrepresented Nations and Peoples Workshop Lewis & Clark Law School 1; Abdullah, Abdurisaq Abdurahman, 'Legal Basis for Unilateral Secession of Somaliland from Somalia'(2023) 2(1) International Journal of Geopolitics and Governance 55

⁵¹ Nathan Yost, 'In The Shadows Of Sovereignty: An Analysis Of The Legality Of The Memorandum Of Understanding Between Ethiopia and the Memorandum Of Understanding Between Ethiopia and Somaliland' (2025) 40(1) American University International Law Review 1255

⁵² Gedifew Sewenet Yigzaw, 'Balancing National Priorities: Ethiopia's Ankara Declaration and Its Implications for Diplomatic Success A Commentary' (2024) 6(1) Pan African Journal of Governance and Development 193

⁵³ Salim Said Salim, Maritime Access and Sovereignty: 'A Legal Analysis of the Ankara Declaration between Ethiopia and Somalia' (2024) Somali Institute for Development Research and Analysis Institute 1

⁵⁴ Tilahun Adamu Zewudie, Decoding the Ankara Declaration: Implications for diplomatic, security affairs past and future (2025) unpublished.

⁵⁵ Bravin Onditi, 'The Ankara Initiative: Turkey's Diplomatic Triumph in the Ethiopia-Somalia Conflict' International Institute for Strategic Studies (17 December 2024) <<https://horninstitute.org/the-ankara-initiative-turkeys-diplomatic-triumph-in-the-ethiopia-somalia-conflict/>> accessed on 31 July 2025

⁵⁶ Aman Obsiye, 'The Ethiopia-Somaliland Naval Base Deal is a Violation of International Law' Minnesota Journal of International Law (16 February 2024) < <https://minnjil.org/2024/02/16/the-ethiopia-somaliland-naval-base-deal-is-a-violation-of-international-law/>> accessed on 31 July 2025

⁵⁷ Derek Wong, 'Sovereignty Sunk: The Position of Sinking States at International Law' (2013) 14 Melbourne Journal of International Law 1

⁵⁸ Montevideo Convention on Rights and Duties of States, opened for signature 26 December 1933, 165 LNTS 19 (entered into force 26 December 1934)

international law in the state formation system.⁵⁹ However, the fourth criteria remained the source of departure in international legal scholarship.⁶⁰ Hence, some authors contend that capacity to enter into international relations is not a prerequisite for the creation of the states; rather it's the consequence of state creation.⁶¹ Somaliland has defined territory which was established during British colonial rule in 1960.⁶² Somaliland has an area of approximately 176,119 square kilometers bordered by The Gulf of Aden in the North, Djibouti in the Northwest, Ethiopia in the West and South and Somalia in the East.⁶³ According to the population census conducted in 2009 Somaliland has approximately 3.8 million populations, 55% is pastoralist and 45% is resided in urban and rural areas.⁶⁴

Beside this, Somaliland has a functional and effective government that exercises its power over all the claimed territory of Somaliland; moreover, there is a peaceful transition of power and Somaliland has held relatively democratic national elections since 2003.⁶⁵ Regarding the fourth requirement, Somaliland has a diplomatic relationship with several States. Somaliland has diplomatic representatives in the USA, Canada, UK, Sweden, France, Norway, Belgium, Ethiopia, Djibouti, Ghana, Kenya, South Sudan, South Africa and Yemen.⁶⁶ Similarly, Denmark, Ethiopia, USA, Djibouti, Kenya, Turkey, UK, Taiwan and UAE have diplomatic representatives in Hargeisa.⁶⁷ Moreover Somaliland has a diplomatic relationship with the European Union in the area of education, health, military and promotion of democracy.⁶⁸ The travel documents of Somaliland are recognized by 20 countries including Ethiopia, South Africa, Djibouti, Uganda, UK, USA, Sweden, Kenya, Tanzania, Nepal, Belgium and Germany.⁶⁹

⁵⁹ Abdulfattah Abdulrazaq & Ram Nabee, 'The Role of the Classical Criteria for Establishing and Recognizing of new States by the International Community' (2020) 8(8) *International Research Journal of Commerce and Law* 1

⁶⁰ Sascha Dov Bachmann & Martinas Prazauskas, 'The Status of Unrecognized Quasi-States and Their Responsibilities Under the Montevideo Convention' (2019) 52(3) *The International Lawyer* 393

⁶¹ Ali Zounuzy Zadeh, 'International Law and the Criteria of Statehood: The Sustainability of the Declaratory and Constitutive Theories as the Method for Assessing the Creation and Continued Existence of States' (LL.M Thesis, Tilburg University 2022)

⁶² Nikola Pijovic, 'To Be or Not to Be: Rethinking the Possible Repercussions of Somaliland's International Statehood Recognition' (2014) 14(4) *African Studies Quarterly* 1

⁶³ Mariel Ferragamo and Claire Klobucista, 'Somaliland: The Horn of Africa Breakaway State' *Council on Foreign Relations* (21 January 2025) <<https://www.cfr.org/backgrounder/somaliland-horn-africas-breakaway-state>> accessed on 9 June 2025

⁶⁴ Mustafe Mohamed H. Dahir, 'Non Recognition of Somaliland in International Law and its Legal Implication for Foreign Investment' (LL.M Thesis, University of Pretoria 2012)

⁶⁵ Gulaid Yusuf Idaan, 'A Legal and Diplomatic Analysis of Somaliland's Quest for International Recognition Modern Diplomacy' <<https://modern diplomacy.eu/2024/07/04/a-legal-and-diplomatic-analysis-of-somalilands-quest-for-international-recognition/>> accessed on 10 June 2025

⁶⁶ Wikipedia, 'Foreign Relations of Somaliland' retrieved from <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Foreign_relations_of_Somaliland> accessed on 30 May 2025

⁶⁷ Ibid

⁶⁸ Cesar Garcia & Pablo Arconada, 'The Role of the European Union in a Non-Recognized Context: The Case of Somaliland (1991-2018)' (2021) 1 *Sociology and Social Work Review* 39

⁶⁹ Wikipedia, 'Somaliland Passport' accessed from <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Somaliland_passport> accessed on 31 July 2025

Nevertheless, Dejen Yemane contends that Somaliland has not fulfilled the criteria of the capacity to enter into international relations hence; it has no sufficient diplomatic representatives and has not participated in full international diplomacy.⁷⁰ Entities which invoked external self-determination are ready to engage in any diplomatic relationship. Therefore, their capacity to enter into foreign relations is depended upon by the desire of the international community. The desire of the international community to engage in diplomatic relationships with entities which invoked external self-determination is based on their national interest. Owing to this, the capacity of entities to enter into international relations should be determined by the competency of the government to engage in international relations independently rather than proving practical realities. Somaliland has set up the institution called the Ministry of Foreign Affairs and International Cooperation to engage in international relations and diplomacy. Furthermore, Somaliland has an effective and independent government to engage in international relations.

The AU has refrained from recognizing Somaliland due to the fear that recognizing Somaliland may Balkanize the continent of Africa.⁷¹ Paradoxically, AU recognized South Sudan's external self-determination on July 27, 2011.⁷² Similarly the Africa Union has admitted Western Sahara as 43rd members of AU and recognized it as an independent Sovereign state in 1982 notwithstanding that Morocco has still claimed it as a part of its territory.⁷³ The USA has refused to recognize Somaliland due to the fear that recognizing Somaliland will jeopardize its diplomatic relationship with African states, Somalia and Arab Countries and will destabilize the Horn of Africa.⁷⁴ However, currently there is a report that the Donald Trump administration is looking to formally recognize Somaliland in exchange for establishing a naval base in Berbera.⁷⁵ China has abstained from engaging

⁷⁰ Sewasew Podcasts Network, የዓለም አቀፍ ሕግ እና የኢትዮጵያ የባህር በር ጥያቄ: ሰማሌላንድ እና ኤርትራ ከአቶ ደጀን የማነ ጋር-ክፍል ሁለት [International Law and Ethiopia's quest to Access the Sea: Somaliland and Eritrea with Degenie Yemane Part Two February] accessed from <<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TzQi-iMGRg&list=PPSV>> accessed on 30 May 2025

⁷¹ Adam Daud Ahmed, 'Op-ed: AU's Recognition Dilemma: Why Somaliland deserves its place among African states with a case stronger than Western Sahara's' Addis Standard (Addis Abeba, 20 February 2025) <<https://addisstandard.com/aus-recognition-dilemma-why-somaliland-deserves-its-place-among-african-states-with-a-case-stronger-than-western-saharas/>> accessed on 29 May 2025

⁷² Keitany Philip, 'The African Union Mission In South Sudan: A case Study of South Sudan' (MA Thesis, University of Nairobi, November 2016)

⁷³ Ikenna Ukpabi Unya, 'Western Sahara as the last African Colony: The Role of Nigeria and the African Union in the Liberation of the last Colonial Territory in Africa' (2020) 2(1) Hallmark Journal of Management and Social Sciences 1

⁷⁴ Abdi Latif Dahir, 'African Breakaway State Offers U.S. a Chance to Stick It to China' The New York Times (New York, 12 April 2025) <<https://www.nytimes.com/2025/04/12/world/africa/somaliland-trump-military-base.html>> accessed on 15 September 2025

⁷⁵ 'Donald Trump set to recognize African state as official country, says ex-Tory minister after holding talks' The Independent (London, 19 November 2024) <<https://www.the-independent.com/news/uk/politics/trump-somaliland-new-country-gavin-williamson-b2648376.html>> accessed on 10 June 2025; Maxwell Webb, 'There's a rare opportunity to deepen US-Somaliland ties: But several obstacles stand in the way' Atlantic Council (Washington, D.C, 17 December 2024)

diplomatic relations with Somaliland due to the dread that such an act will open the door to other states to recognize Taiwan and may threaten one China policy.⁷⁶

Contemporarily, States have applied international law when it is convenient to their national interest and utilized it as an ideological weapon to secure their economic and political interest.⁷⁷ Murphy contends that the USA utilizes international law and international institutions to secure its economic and political interest in the world.⁷⁸ Resultantly, it's inevitable that States use recognition as a means to secure their political ideology and they recognize entities as a state only when it's convenient to their national interest.⁷⁹ For instance, the USA has refused to recognize Palestine due to its political interest in the Middle East and its strategic alliance with Israel. Conversely, it engaged in diplomatic relations with Taiwan though the USA has not formally recognized Taiwan as an independent sovereign state.⁸⁰

Egypt, the historical rival of Ethiopia has condemned the MOU on the ground that the MOU is a blatant violation of territorial integrity and sovereignty of Somalia.⁸¹ However, in 2019 Egypt has offered a proposal to Somaliland to establish a military base in Somaliland in the exchange for international recognition, though the offer is rejected by Somaliland due to the fear that the agreement may jeopardize its diplomatic relationship with Ethiopia.⁸² Resultantly, recognition is a political act of the state.⁸³ Therefore, the quest of Somaliland for international recognition is ignored by AU and international community due to political implication rather than legal impediments and

<<https://www.atlanticcouncil.org/blogs/africasource/theres-a-rare-opportunity-to-deepen-us-somaliland-ties-but-several-obstacles-stand-in-the-way/>> accessed on 9 June 2025

⁷⁶ Abdulkadir Khalif, 'China Rejects Taiwan bid for Diplomatic Relations with Somaliland' *The East African* (Nairobi, 5 June 2020) <<https://www.theeastafrican.co.ke/tea/news/east-africa/china-rejects-taiwan-bid-for-diplomatic-relations-with-somaliland-1445274>> accessed on 16 May 2025

⁷⁷ Shirley V. Scott, 'International Law as Ideology: Theorizing the Relationship between International Law and International Politics' (1994) 5 *European Journal of International Law* 313

⁷⁸ Sean D Murphy, *United State Practice in International law Volume 1: 1999-2001* (Cambridge University Press, 2003)

⁷⁹ Suzanne Kelly Panganiban, 'Palestinian Statehood: A Study of Statehood through the Lens of the Montevideo Convention' (MA Thesis, Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University 2015)

⁸⁰ Aljazeera, 'Mapping Which Countries Recognize Palestine in 2025' accessed from <<https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2025/4/10/mapping-which-countries-recognise-palestine-in-2025>> accessed on 9 June 2025; Reuters, 'Explainer: Relations between Taiwan and the United States' accessed from <<https://www.reuters.com/world/relations-between-taiwan-united-states-2024-07-17/>> accessed on 9 June 2025

⁸¹ Mohammed El-Said, 'Egypt condemns Ethiopia's deal with Somaliland as violation to Somalia's sovereignty' *Egypt Daily News* (Dokki, 4 January 2024) <<https://www.dailynewsegypt.com/2024/01/04/egypt-condemns-ethiopias-deal-with-somaliland-as-violation-to-somalias-sovereignty/>> accessed on 12 May 2025

⁸² 'Ethiopia angered Egypt's plan to set up Military Base in Somaliland' (Garowe Online, 20 July 2020) <<https://www.garoweonline.com/en/world/africa/ethiopia-angered-with-egypts-plans-to-set-up-military-base-in-somaliland>> accessed on 12 May 2025

⁸³ Malcolm N. Shaw, *International law* (Cambridge University Press, 5th ed, 2003) 1, 186; Michele Pitta, *Statehood and Recognition: The case of Palestine* (MA Thesis, University of Barcelona 2018)

incapability of Somaliland. Accordingly, the author argues that recognition should not be a judgmental prerequisite for the creation of new states.

b. The principle of uti possidetis juris and the findings of the African Union Fact-Finding Mission in Somaliland

The principle of uti possidetis justifies Somaliland recognition.⁸⁴ 'Respect of borders existing on achievement of independence' is one of the cardinal principles of the Constitutive Act of the Africa Union.⁸⁵ Moreover in the Cairo Resolution all African States including Somalia agreed to inherit colonial boundaries.⁸⁶ Somaliland and Somalia have defined boundaries established by their colonizers.⁸⁷ Consequently, Somalia has an international obligation to accept and respect the territorial integrity and sovereignty of Somaliland.

For several years Somaliland has requested the Africa Union to set up a fact-finding mission in Somaliland. Accordingly, the Africa Union established a fact finding Mission in 2005 to investigate factual situations in Somaliland, and the commission found that Somaliland has fulfilled all prerequisites which are required for international recognition.⁸⁸ According to the fact finding mission of the Africa Union, Somaliland has defined territory inherited from the colonial rule of British, population of estimated 3.5 million resided in Somaliland and the constitution it serves as a basic law and requires separation of power among organs of the government.⁸⁹ Moreover, the Fact Finding Mission proved that 'the union between Somaliland and Somalia was never ratified and also malfunctioned when it went into action from 1960 to 1990, making Somaliland's search for recognition historically unique and self-justified in African political history.'⁹⁰

However, the Africa Union refrained from recognizing Somaliland as an independent sovereign State by fearing that recognizing Somaliland will encourage other rebels to secede from their parent states and secession will spread over the continent of Africa. In this regard the Fact Finding Mission recommended to the Union that the issue of Somaliland should not be aligned with the notion of "opening Pandora box," instead

⁸⁴ Michael Farrell, 'Manufacturing Territorial Integrity with the International Court of Justice: The Somaliland-Puntland Dispute and Uti Possidetis' (2012) 11(4) Washington University Global Studies Law Review 817

⁸⁵ Constitutive Act of the African Union (adopted 11 July 2000, entered into force 26 May 2001) art. 4(a)

⁸⁶ Abdusalam M. Issa-Salwe & Abdullahi Salah, 'Why Has Somaliland Not Been Recognized as A Sovereign State' (2023) 10(4) Advance in Social Science Research Journal 1

⁸⁷ Dominique Jacquin, 'Nationalism and Secession in the Horn of Africa: A Critique of the Ethnic Interpretation' (LLD Doctoral Thesis, London University 2002)

⁸⁸ Stephen M. Schwartz, 'The African Union Should Resolve Somaliland's Status' Foreign Policy Research Institute (Philadelphia, 8 November 2021) <<https://www.fpri.org/article/2021/11/the-african-union-should-resolve-somalilands-status/>> accessed on 3 July 2025

⁸⁹ African Union, 'AU Fact-Finding Mission to Somaliland Resume (30 April to 4 May 2005)' accessed from <https://www.americanrhetoric.com/speeches/PDFFiles/au-fact-finding-mission-to-somaliland-30-april-to-4-may-2005.pdf>

⁹⁰ Peter Pham, 'Somaliland at 20' Atlantic Council (Washington D.C, 18 May 2011) <<https://www.atlanticcouncil.org/blogs/new-atlanticist/somaliland-at-20/>> accessed on 3 July 2025

the Union should set up a special mechanism to deal with the case of Somaliland.⁹¹ Furthermore, the Fact Finding Mission recommended the Union that the recognition of Somaliland should be addressed based on the historical background, moral sentiment and aspiration of the people to be independent sovereign State⁹². Ultimately, the author of this article recommends that the Africa Union should endorse new continental laws which regulate how the African States would govern external self-determination and considerations which should be taken into account in the recognition of States. For instance, the European Union has adopted guidelines to regulate recognition in Eastern Europe and the dissolution of the former USSR.⁹³

c. International law precludes only premature recognition

Premature recognition refers to recognition of an entity as a State before satisfying the preconditions of statehood.⁹⁴ International law precludes only premature recognition hence, such recognition is against the sovereignty and the territorial integrity of parent States.⁹⁵ In this sense recognizing entities as a state which fulfilled the preconditions of statehood is not against international law. As it is proved by the Africa Union Fact Finding Mission in Somaliland and International Crisis Group, Somaliland has fulfilled all preconditions of statehood stipulated in the Montevideo convention.⁹⁶ Therefore as long as Somaliland meets all preconditions of statehood, recognizing Somaliland as an independent sovereign state is not a violation of international law.

d. Dissolution of *the* Union between Somaliland and Somalia

Though the people of Somali have shared common cultural and linguistic values, Somalia has never existed as an independent political sovereign state until 1960.⁹⁷ Somaliland has enjoyed five days of statehood and has been recognized by 35 countries including all Permanent Members of the United Nation Security Council as an independent political entity on the date of gaining its independence in 1960.⁹⁸ However after five days of

⁹¹Nikola Pijovic, 'Seceding but not Succeeding: African International Relations and Somaliland's lacking international recognition' (2013) 19 Croatian International Relation Review 5

⁹² Garth Abraham, 'Lines Upon Maps: Africa and the Sanctity of African Boundaries' (2007) 15 (1) African Journal of International and Comparative Law 61

⁹³ Christian Hillgruber, 'The Admission of New States to the International Community' (1998) 9 European Journal of International Law 494

⁹⁴ Kemal Gider, 'Political Realities of Recognition of States Contrary to the Bindings of International Law' (2020) 53 Cornell International Law Journal Online 28

⁹⁵ H. Lauterpacht, 'Recognition of State in International Law' (1994) 53(3) The Yale Law Journal 385; Francois Finck, 'The State between Fact and Law: The Role of Recognition and the Conditions under which it is Granted in the Creation of new States' (2016) Polish Year Book of International Law 52

⁹⁶ International Crisis Group, Somaliland: Time for African Union Leadership Crisis Group Africa Report N°110, 23 May 2006 1, 11.

⁹⁷ Peter Pbam, 'The Somaliland Exception: Lessons on Post conflict State Building from the Part of the Former Somalia That Works' (2012) 3(3) Marine Corps University Journal 1

⁹⁸ Temesgen Sisay Beyene, 'Declaration of Statehood by Somaliland and the Effects of Non-Recognition under International Law' (2019) Beijing Law Review 196

enjoying statehood, Somaliland and Somalia were united in 1960 to establish Greater Somalia.⁹⁹ In this sense Somaliland and Somalia are two separate political entities before their agreement to unite and the Republic of Somalia is created by international treaty.¹⁰⁰ Consequently, the union of two states resembles de facto confederation.

Therefore, the ongoing demand of Somaliland for international recognition should not align with the issue of secession from Somalia. Accordingly, the international community and institution should not perceive the demand of Somaliland for international recognition as a unilateral declaration of independence or secession; instead, the international community should perceive it as the dissolution of union between Somalia and Somaliland.

Besides this, the union of Somaliland and Somalia is a defective unification. Hence, as it's proved by the Fact Finding Mission of Africa Union in Somaliland, the Law of the Union adopted by Somaliland legislature on 27 June 1960 is not signed by the National Assembly of Somalia notwithstanding the Law of Union requires signature by Somalia representatives for its enforcement.¹⁰¹ Conversely, in 1961 Somalia enacted an act of union which was not signed and ratified by Somaliland.¹⁰² Therefore, the law of union crafted by Somaliland and the act of union endorsed by Somalia to establish the Republic of Somalia is invalid in the eyes of international law; hence both treaties are the unilateral acts of two states.¹⁰³ As a result, there is no valid and binding legal document signed between two states to establish the Republic of Somalia.

Furthermore, there are several unions which are easily dissolved without the need for international recognition to retain their former statehood. Firstly, Senegambia, the union between Senegal and Gambia is easily dissolved due to the desire of Senegal to end the union in 1989 without the need for international recognition in retaining former international legal status.¹⁰⁴ Secondly, Mali Federation, the union between Senegal and Mali, was dissolved due to the decision of Senegal to establish its own independent state in 1960 and two states acquired international legal status without recognition.¹⁰⁵ Similarly, in the case of Somaliland, Somaliland has withdrawn its consent from the union to regain its international legal personality.

⁹⁹ Dimitrios Lalos, 'Between Statehood and Somalia: Reflections of Somaliland Statehood' (2011) 10(4) Washington University Global Studies Law Review 789

¹⁰⁰ Christiane E. Philipp, 'Somalia Very Special Case' (2005) 9 Max Planck Yearbook of United Nations Law 517

¹⁰¹ Horn Diplomat, 'The Case for Somaliland Recognition by Mahamoud Adan Jama' accessed from <<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ACa7cp1tXdI&list=PPSV>> accessed on 28 May 2025

¹⁰² Ahmed H Nur, 'A short Briefing Paper: Does Somaliland has a legal ground for seeking international recognition?' (2011) (unpublished)

¹⁰³ Peter Roethke, 'The right to secede under international Law: In case of Somaliland' (2011) Journal of International Service 36

¹⁰⁴ Awosusi Oladotun Emmanuel & Muhammed Lenn, 'An Analysis of Latent Factors Influencing Gambia-Senegal Relations beyond Colonial Dichotomy' (2019) 75 International Affairs and Global Strategy 59

¹⁰⁵ Katharina Wurzer, 'The Mali-Federation: A Pan-African Endeavour? Reflections on Pan-Africanism and Nationalism in Times of Decolonization' (2020) 20 Vienna Journal of African Studies 55

e. The principle of self-determination justifies Somaliland's quest for statehood

International law allows entities to exercise their external self-determination when they are denied from enjoying their internal self-determination.¹⁰⁶ Somalilanders are denied from exercising internal self-determination under the regime of Seid Bare military dictatorship.¹⁰⁷ Moreover the regime committed grave human right violations on Somalilanders. The primary justification of international law for the preclusion of external self-determination is to protect the sovereignty and territorial integrity of the mother state. As the author mentioned above, Somaliland's quest of self-determination is not contrary with the territorial integrity and sovereignty of Somalia. Beside this, Somaliland self-determination has a unique nature. Hence Somalilanders are invoking their pre-existing rights of statehood. Therefore, the case of Somaliland should be looked at in a special way.

The precondition of statehood for state formation is reluctant only in the creation of new independent sovereign States.¹⁰⁸ In the case of Somaliland, Somalilanders are not claiming to create a new independent political entity; instead, they are asserting their former rights of statehood. Accordingly, the international community including African actors should perceive the quest of Somaliland beyond the ambit of secession. As a result, Ethio-Somaliland maritime accord in exchange for recognition is not a violation of international law. However, though recognizing Somaliland is not against international law Ethiopia should abstain from recognizing Somaliland due to two justifications. Firstly, recognizing Somaliland at this time when several rebel forces are at war with the federal government of Ethiopia threaten Ethiopia's territorial integrity and sovereignty. Secondly, the international community like the UN, USA, AU, China and EU reject MOU and call Ethiopia to respect the sovereignty of Somalia.¹⁰⁹ As long as international law is intertwined with international politics Ethiopia should take into account global politics and requires strong diplomacy to obtain support from the rest of the world.

4. ETHIOPIA'S CLAIM OF OWNERSHIP OVER ASSAB AND INTERNATIONAL LAW

On 23 October 2023 Abiy Ahmed addressed Ethiopia's legitimate right to access the sea by invoking the famous speech of Ras Alula Abanega it states that 'the Red Sea itself has been and will continue to be Ethiopia's natural boundary.'¹¹⁰ In addition to this, the

¹⁰⁶ Matthew Saul, 'The Normative Status of Self-Determination in International Law: A Formula for Uncertainty in the Scope and Content of the Right' (2011) 11(4) Human Right Law Review 609

¹⁰⁷ Abdillahi Mohamed Bile, 'A Legal Analysis of Somaliland's Quest for Statehood under International Law' (2024) 4(1) Journal of Modern Law and Policy 1

¹⁰⁸ Ibid

¹⁰⁹ BBC, 'Ethiopia-Somaliland deal: Can the Horn of Africa rift be healed?' accessed from <<https://www.bbc.com/news/world-africa-67911057>> accessed on 2 September 2025

¹¹⁰ Fana Television

government and government affiliated Medias repeatedly have asserted Ethiopia's legitimate and historical rights of ownership over Assab. Accordingly, it's straightforward to comprehend that claiming ownership over Assab is another alternative approach invoked by Ethiopia to realize its quest of access to the sea. As a result, Ethiopia's ambition to access the sea in general and Ethiopia's claim of ownership over Assab in particular creates vigorous contestation between Ethiopia and Eritrea.¹¹¹

Ethiopia's claim of ownership over Assab is based on historical and demographic realities.¹¹² Abebe and Yared Haile Mariam have argued that international law allows Ethiopia to invoke its legitimate and historical right of ownership over Assab. Similarly, Prof. Negussay Ayele argued that Ethiopia has legitimate sovereign right over Assab by invoking historical and demographic justifications.¹¹³ Up to the knowledge of the author, Dereje Zeleke is the only Ethiopian legal expert who ignored Ethiopia's claims of ownership over Assab by scrutinizing international law.¹¹⁴ Dereje argued that unconditional acceptance of colonial treaties to delimit and demarcate boundary dispute in Algiers Agreement by EPRDF has locked all possible ways to restore Assab to Ethiopia.¹¹⁵ Moreover, Dereje argued that unilateral statement of former Ethiopian Prime Minister Melese Zenawi on the issue of Assab has created international obligation on Ethiopia to accept Assab as a territorial part of Eritrea.¹¹⁶ However, the way in which Ethiopia deprived its historical right over the Red Sea legitimizes Ethiopia's ongoing quest over Assab.

Historical documents demonstrate Ethiopia's presence in Assab. Ethiopia lost its legitimate and historical rights over the port due to a political conspiracy between the TPLF and the Eritrean People's Liberation Front. During the EPRDF era, asserting ownership over Assab was precluded. Several scholars warned the EPRDF to consider Ethiopia's legitimate rights during the Eritrean secession and the subsequent boundary dispute proceedings led by the EEBC. However, the EPRDF deliberately ignored these historical rights and signed the Algiers Agreement, which denied Ethiopia any presence along the Red Sea coast. Ethiopia's claim of ownership over Assab was never a mystery; it was like a concealed bomb. For over thirty years, Ethiopians have repeatedly invoked their rights over the port. Accordingly, it was clear that Ethiopia's quest for Assab would

¹¹¹ Gebre Hiwet Tesfagiorgis, 'Access to the Sea in the Context of Eritrea and Ethiopia' (2022) accessed from <<https://eri-platform.org/swfiles/files/Access-to-the-Sea-in-the-Context-of-Eritrea-and-Ethiopia.pdf>>

¹¹² Gebrerufael Girmay, 'The Necessity of Assab Port to Ethiopia' (Tigrai Online, 21 August 2016) <<https://www.tigraionline.com/articles/necessity-of-assab-port.html>> accessed on 14 September 2025

¹¹³ Negussay Ayele, 'Assab as Symbol for the Restoration of Ethiopia's Natural Seacoast' Ethiopian.Com (1 October 2000) < https://www.ethiopians.com/Views/Negussay_Aseeb_Symbol.htm> accessed on 8 July 2025

¹¹⁴ Andafta, አሰብ ወደ ኢትዮጵያ የምትመራበት የህግ ተስፋ የለም (There is no Legal hope to Restore Assab to Ethiopia) accessed from <<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=qcmjPUo3FtY>>

¹¹⁵ Borkena, 'No way to make Assab part of Ethiopia,' says a legal scholar' accessed from <<https://borkena.com/2019/06/01/no-way-to-make-assab-part-of-ethiopia-says-a-legal-scholar/>> accessed on 8 July 2025

¹¹⁶ Ibid.

eventually be officially reignited by a future regime. Currently, Ethiopia is claiming Assab by citing historical realities and the irresponsible actions of the EPRDF. Nevertheless, international law principles, the Algiers Agreement, and the ruling of the EEBC will challenge the realization of Ethiopia's quest.

a. Unconditional recognition of Eritrean external self-determination by the transitional government

Astoundingly, Ethiopia is pioneering and the first State in the world that provide unconditional support to its former province, to exercise its external self-determination through internationally supervised referendum.¹¹⁷ The Transitional Government recognized Eritrean external self-determination by writing letters to the UN and AU.¹¹⁸ Eritrea is territorially defined by the UN Resolution 390(v) as 'the territory of Eritrea, including the islands, is that of the former Italian colony of Eritrea.'¹¹⁹ EPRDF recognized Eritrea within its 'colonially defined territory' without saying anything about Ethiopia's legitimate and historical title over the coastal area of the Red Sea.

However, unconditional acceptance of Eritrean external self-determination is not valid and binding. Hence, the Transitional Government does not have a mandate to recognize Eritrea and engaged in international relations which are against Ethiopia's sovereignty.¹²⁰ Indeed there is no generally accepted international law which precludes a transitional government from entering into international relations. More importantly, the Transitional Government Establishment Proclamation of Ethiopia empowered the transitional government to engage in international relations based on the principle of sovereignty and equality of states.¹²¹ Accordingly, some may contend that the Transitional Government is empowered to engage in international relations and Ethiopia is still binding on it.

However, as stated under article 3 of the Transitional Charter it serves as a supreme law of the land, the Transitional Government is empowered only to conduct international relations which are not contrary to Ethiopia's sovereignty and interests of the people.¹²² Recognizing Ethiopia's province (Eritrea) as an independent sovereign state violates Ethiopia's sovereignty and interest of the people. Accordingly, recognition

¹¹⁷ Dereje Zeleke Mekonen, *The Ethio-Eritrean Boundary Dispute: Anomalies and Imperatives for Peaceful Relations* (2019) 3 *International Law Series* 47

¹¹⁸ Costantinos Berhutesfa Costantino, 'An Alpenglow of Peace & Prosperity beams over the Greater Horn of Africa & the Red Sea enclave Beyond the Impasse in Eritrea and Ethiopia' (2018) Lecture given at the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Ethiopia

¹¹⁹ Yohannes Haile and others , 'Eritrean Sovereignty and Ethiopia's quest for sea access' (2025) Red Sea Task Force

¹²⁰ Prime Media, ሜጀር ጄኔራል ተሾመ ገመቹ ከፕራይም ሜዲያ ጋር በነበራቸው ቆይታ የሰጡት ምላሽና ማብራሪያ (Response and Clarification of Major General Teshome Gemechu in his Conversation with Prime Media) accessed from <<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MVFKNr1KCsA> > accessed on 3 November 2025

¹²¹ Transitional Period Charter of Ethiopia, Proclamation No. 1/1991, FED. NEGARIT GAZETA 1st Year No.1 Addis Abeba, July 22, 1991

¹²² Ibid

of Eritrea by the transitional government of Ethiopia is not valid and binding in the eye of international law. Here some may contend that Ethiopia cannot invoke the transitional charter as a defense for its international obligation and consequently validate the mandate of the transitional government to recognize Eritrea. However, there is an exceptional circumstance in which states can invoke their domestic law for the excuse of international obligations.¹²³ As stated under article 46 of Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties, states can invoke their domestic law when 'violation was manifest and concerned a rule of its internal law of fundamental importance.'¹²⁴

Therefore, to invoke domestic law as a defense, two cumulative preconditions must be fulfilled: the violation must concern a rule of internal law of fundamental importance, and the violation must be objectively manifest to any State conducting itself in good faith. In the Ethio-Eritrean context, the recognition of Eritrea as a sovereign state constituted a blatant violation of the Transitional Charter, which served as the constitution at the time. Furthermore, the incompetence of Ethiopia's Transitional Government to grant such recognition should have been evident to states negotiating in good faith. Consequently, Ethiopia's recognition of Eritrea is invalid within the framework of international law.

As stated in the UN Resolution, 'the rights and claims of Ethiopia based on geographical, historical, ethnic or economic reasons including in particular Ethiopia's legitimate need for adequate access to the sea was one of the factors for the creation of federation.'¹²⁵ Accordingly, Ethiopian Prime Minister Abiy Ahmed in his discussion with the legislative body and some scholars asserts the legitimacy of Ethiopia's ongoing quest over the Red Sea by invoking the UN resolution.¹²⁶ However, although Ethiopia's legitimate right over the Red sea was acknowledged by this resolution, EPRDF has relinquished Ethiopia's legitimate and historical rights by recognizing Eritrea as an independent sovereign state without claiming Assab. More appallingly, instead of claiming ownership over Assab, EPRDF signed a transit and port service agreement that allows Ethiopia to use the port of Assab.¹²⁷ Similarly, during the negotiation process of the Algiers Agreement, Ethiopia claimed the Ethio-Eritrea Claim Commission to restore properties which were illegally detained and expropriated in Massawa and Assab by

¹²³ Richard D. Kearney, 'Internal Limitations on External Commitments - Article 46 of the Treaties Convention' (1970) 4(1) *International Lawyer* 1

¹²⁴ Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties (adopted 23 May 1969, entered into force 27 January 1980), art, 46(2)

¹²⁵ Text of Resolution 390 A (V) adopted on December 2, 1950 by the General Assembly of the United Nations, 390 (V) Eritrea: Report of the United Nations Commission on Eritrea; Report of the Interim Committee of the General Assembly on the report of the United Nations Commission for Eritrea.

¹²⁶ Damtew Tesema, 'International Law and Ethiopia's right access to the Sea outlet November' (Damtew Tesema Blog, 19 November 2017) <<https://damtew599827934.wordpress.com/2017/11/19/international-law-and-ethiopias-right-access-to-the-sea/>> accessed on 10 July 2025

¹²⁷ Marta Belete Hailu, 'Mending Ethio-Eritrea Trade Relations: the Why and How' (2019) 3 *International Law Series* 130

Eritrea.¹²⁸ Indeed the dissolution of the Ethio-Eritrea federation in 1962 invalidates and rescinded the UN Resolution 390(v).¹²⁹

b. The principle of *uti possidetis juris*

The principle of *uti possidetis* is universally binding international customary law within the context of colonization to delimit boundary disputes.¹³⁰ The principle advocates that international boundaries are formed based on boundaries and frontiers of the colonial era.¹³¹ This principle can be applied beyond the context of colonization, particularly in case of self-determination and dissolutions of States.¹³² In case of dissolutions of States *uti possidetis* is defined as ‘former internal administrative borders of the federation must remain and become borders of the newly sovereign states.’¹³³ This principle was applied in the dissolution of the Soviet Union, Czechoslovakia and Yugoslavia.¹³⁴ In the context of self-determination this principle is defined as the newly created state inherits its former internal administrative boundaries from the parent state.

Erroneously, EPRDF has accepted Eritrea as a colony of Ethiopia.¹³⁵ Owing to this, in the Algiers Agreement, Ethiopia and Eritrea have agreed to delimit boundary disputes based on the principle of *uti possidetis* within the context of colonization. Article 4 of the Agreement stated that ‘the parties are agreed to reaffirm the principle of respect for the borders existing at independence as stated in resolution AHG/Res. 16(1) adopted by the OAU Summit in Cairo in 1964.’¹³⁶ Therefore, in this agreement EPRDF agreed to grant all territories which were under Italian colonial rule to Eritrea. Assab was under the control of Italy from 1882 to 1942.¹³⁷ Dr. Yacob argued that as long as Assab was the autonomous province of Ethiopia, the principle of *uti possidetis* and 1964 Cairo

¹²⁸ Wondimagegn Tadesse Goshu, ‘Ethiopia-Eritrea Claims for Loss, Damage or Injury and the Claims Commission: Lessons for Future Bilateral Relations’ (2019) 3 International Law Series 7

¹²⁹ Isaias Teklia Berhe, ‘Anomalous or legitimate covetousness: Scholarly echoes of Ethiopia’s claim of sovereign right for access to the sea under international law’ (2016) 1 International Conference on Eritrean Studies 543

¹³⁰ Gideon Boas, *Public International Law: Contemporary Principles and Perspectives* (Edward Elgar Publishing Limited, 1st ed, 2012) 1, 200.

¹³¹ *Ibid*

¹³² Bande Gulbert Mbah Tarh, ‘Tenets of *Uti Possidetis* as a Panacea in Resolving Boundary Disputes in Africa: A Lesson from the Bakassi Peninsula Dispute’ (2022) 9(1) International Journal of Trend in Research and Development 28

¹³³ Lauri M Alksoo, ‘Post-Soviet Eurasia, *Uti Possidetis* and the Clash between Universal and Russian led Regional Understandings of International Law’ (2021) 53 International Law and Politics 787

¹³⁴ Abraham Bell & Eugene Kontorovich, ‘Palestine, *Uti Possidetis Juris*, and the Borders of Israel’ (2016) 58 Arizona Law Review 638

¹³⁵ Yohannes Aberra, ‘Ethiopia’s Access to Sea: Political Machinations and the Quest for Justice’ (News Addis, 6 November 2024) <<https://newsaddis.com/ethiopias-access-to-sea-political-machinations-and-the-quest-for-justice/>> accessed on 2 July 2025

¹³⁶ Agreement Between the Government of the Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia and the Government of the State of Eritrea, December 12, 2000 Article 4. [Hear in after Algiers Agreement]

¹³⁷ Morten Jerven & Jacon Weisdorf, ‘A Case of its Own? A Review of Italy’s Colonization of Eritrea, 1890-1941’ (2021) African Economic History Working Paper Series No 66/2021

Resolution impose obligation on Eritrea to respect the boundary which demarcated between Eritrea and the province of Assab in 1980.¹³⁸ Reversely, some contend that in the Algiers Agreement Ethiopia is agreed to demarcate Ethio-Eritrea boundary dispute based on colonial treaties which gives ownership for Eritrea over Assab, Dr. Yacob argument will be sound if Ethiopia was agreed to delimit boundary disputes based on the principle of *uti possidetis* within the context of self-determination.

Some authors attempted to buttress the legitimacy of ongoing Ethiopia's claims of ownership over Assab by contending that the principle of *uti possidetis* should be interpreted in consideration of the principle fairness and equity.¹³⁹ In the Algiers Agreement Ethiopia and Eritrea mandated the EEBC to resolve boundary disputes within the existing legal frameworks alone in disregard of the principle of fairness and equity.¹⁴⁰ Resultantly, some may contend that there is no room in which those principles are considered in demarcation and delimitation of Ethio-Eritrea boundary dispute.¹⁴¹ However, no historical document exists that demonstrates that Eritrea was a colony of Ethiopia. Therefore, the Ethio-Eritrea boundary dispute should be settled based on the principle of *uti possidetis* in the context of self-determination in consideration of the principles of fairness and justice. Hence, history demonstrates that Eritrea was a territorial part of Ethiopia and Assab was one of the autonomous provinces.¹⁴² Beside this, in article 4(1) of the Algiers Agreement two states have agreed to use "applicable international laws".¹⁴³ In this sense, the demarcation of Ethi-Eritrea boundary dispute delimitation should not be trapped only on three colonial treaties.

c. The Revival of 1900, 1902 and 1908 Boundary Treaties by Algiers Agreement

Ethiopia signed several boundary treaties with European colonial powers to delimit its boundary with its neighbors.¹⁴⁴ Ethiopia signed 1900, 1902 & 1908 agreements with Italy to delimit boundary demarcation between Ethiopia and Eritrea.¹⁴⁵ However, some Ethiopian scholars contend that those agreements lack validity to delimit the Ethio-

¹³⁸ Yakob Hailemariam, 'አሰብ የማንኛት? የኢትዮጵያ የባህር በር ጥያቄ (ታሪክ አሳታሚ፣ 2010) (Who Does Assab Belong To? Ethiopia's Quest for Access to the Sea)' (Tarik Publishers, 2010) [Hear in After Yacob Hailemariam]

¹³⁹ Biruk Paulos & Temesgen Thomas Halabo, 'Ethiopia's Quest for Access to the Sea: Historical Realities and Legitimate Claims' (2025) 19(2) Mizan Law Review 347

¹⁴⁰ Algiers Agreement art, 4(2)

¹⁴¹ Malcolm N Shaw 'Title, Control, and Closure? The Experience of the Eritrea–Ethiopia Boundary Commission' (2007) 56 (4) International and Comparative Law Quarterly 755

¹⁴² Asrat Sebsbie, 'The Right of Land locked state to access to the sea under International Law: The case of Ethiopia' (LLB Thesis, St. Mary's University 2009)

¹⁴³ Algiers Agreement art, 4(1)

¹⁴⁴ James Kiprono Kibon, 'Examining the Sustainability of Ethiopia's Embryonic Territorial Claim on the Ilemi Triangle' (2019) 7(8) The International Journal of Humanities and Social Science 65

¹⁴⁵ Abbink, G. J, 'Badme and the Ethio-Eritrean Border: The challenge of Demarcation in the Post-war Period Africa' (2003) 58(2) Journal of the International African Institute 219

Eritrea boundary dispute.¹⁴⁶ Hence, firstly emperor Menelik signed the agreements under the influence of Italy and other colonial powers.¹⁴⁷ Secondly, Italy abrogated boundary agreements by invading Ethiopia in 1935.¹⁴⁸ Thirdly, on 10 February 1947 in Paris, Italy agreed with Allied powers and Associated Powers including Ethiopia to relinquish all rights over her former colonies in Africa and Europe.¹⁴⁹

Moreover, Italy agreed to cancel all colonial treaties concluded with her former colonies.¹⁵⁰ By articulating those justifications Ethiopian legal scholars have argued that Ethiopia's ongoing claim of ownership over Assab is not a breach of international law. Beside this, decree number 6/1952 promulgated by Ethiopia to nullify three colonial treaties has invalidated the obligatory nature of those treaties signed with Italy. Indeed, states cannot unilaterally terminate the enforcement of international treaties and cannot invoke their municipal laws to exonerate from international obligation.¹⁵¹ Furthermore, Dr. Yacob argued that Rubattino Shipping Company (an Italian company) had purchased Assab from Afar Sultan without the consent of Emperor Menelik.¹⁵²

Even though Italy has abrogated colonial treaties by invading Ethiopia and Italy has agreed to renounce all rights and claims in Africa, EPRDF has agreed to resume colonial treaties in the Algiers Agreement. Hence, in this agreement two states agreed to delimit boundary disputes based on colonial treaties. The Algiers Agreement has passed all ordinary treaty making processes and ratified by Ethiopia via ratification proclamation number 225/2000.¹⁵³ As stated in article 3 of ratification proclamation the Algiers Agreement began to bind Ethiopia and Eritrea upon the signature of two states.¹⁵⁴ Similarly, the Algiers Agreement prescribes signature as the entry into force of the agreement.¹⁵⁵ The agreement was signed by two states on 12 December 2000.¹⁵⁶

¹⁴⁶ Reyot, ከዶ/ር ያዕቆብ ኃይለማሪያም ጋር የተደረገ ቃለ ምልልስ (Interview with Dr. Yacob Hailemariam on Assab) accessed from <<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yHpF1pVALeg>> accessed on 8 July 2025

¹⁴⁷ Abebe T. Kahsay, 'Ethiopia's Sovereign Right of Access to the Sea under International Law' (LLM Thesis, University of Georgia 2007)

¹⁴⁸ EBC, የኢትዮጵያ የባህር በር ጥያቄ እና ዓለም አቀፍ ህጎች (Ethiopia's Quest to Access the Sea and International Law) accessed from <<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=NspqtQvcFGE&list=PPSV>> accessed on 10 July 2025

¹⁴⁹ Federico Tenca Montini, 'The Burning Border: comparative study of the problem of Trieste and other territorial issues confronted by Italy after defeat in the Second World War' (2019) 51(2) *Journal of the Institute of Croatian History* 233

¹⁵⁰ Ibid

¹⁵¹ Louis B. Sohn & R. R. Baxter, 'Responsibility of States for Injuries to the Economic Interests of Aliens: II. Draft Convention on the International Responsibility of States for Injuries to Aliens' (1961) 55(3) *American Journal of International Law* 548

¹⁵² Yacob Hailemariam

¹⁵³ Peace Agreement between the Government of the Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia and the Government of the State of Eritrea Ratification Proclamation, Proclamation NO. 225/2000, FED. NEGARIT GAZETA 7th Year No. 7 Addis Abeba, December 8, 2000.

¹⁵⁴ Ibid

¹⁵⁵ Algiers Agreement art, 6(1)

¹⁵⁶ Ethio-Eritrea Boundary Commission, Press Release Permanent Court of Arbitration, The Hague, 30 November 2006

Accordingly, some authors contend that colonial treaties (1900, 1902 & 1908) signed between Ethiopia and Italy are still binding.¹⁵⁷ Reversely, by interpreting the phrase “to sign the peace agreement” from article 2 of the proclamation number 225/2000, Zeray Weldesenbet contend that proclamation number 225/2000 gives “a political authorization” alone for the executive organs of the government to sign the Algiers Agreement.¹⁵⁸ As a result, he contends that the Algiers Agreement is not ratified before the parliament and does not impose any obligation on Ethiopia to adhere to it.

Ethiopia would not be compelled by Algiers Agreement which was irresponsibly signed by EPRDF and deprived Ethiopia's legal and historical title over Assab. However, in international treaty law, treaties signed by one government are not terminated upon the change of the government.¹⁵⁹ Consequently, some contend that so long as the agreement is not amended or repealed by two states or the ground for termination of the treaty happens, all consecutive governments of Ethiopia are continued to be bound by the Algiers Agreement. Therefore, the Algiers agreement which was irresponsibly signed by EPRDF is another legal document that will challenge the realization of ongoing Ethiopia's historical and legitimate claims of ownership over Assab.

d. Acceptance of the Algiers Agreement and the Ruling of Ethio-Eritrea Boundary Commission

The Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia and the government of Eritrea have agreed to permanently terminate military hostilities in Algiers in 2000.¹⁶⁰ In the Algiers Agreement, a neutral Boundary Commission was established with the mandate to delimit and demarcate the border disputes in accordance with colonial treaties and applicable international laws.¹⁶¹ Beside this, Ethiopia and Eritrea have agreed that the finding of the commission is final and non-appealable.¹⁶² On 13 April 2002 EEBC disclosed its findings within 125 pages.¹⁶³ However, the commission dissolved itself in November 2007 only after performing the task of delimitations of frontiers in paper without putting

¹⁵⁷ Lantera Nadew Anebo, 'Assessing the Efficacy of African Boundary Delineation Law and Policy: The Case of Ethio– Eritrea Boundary Dispute Settlement' (Doctoral Thesis, Golden Gate University 2016)

¹⁵⁸ Zeray Weldesenbet, 'Disputed Past: 1908 Colonial Treaty Didn't Define Assab Region and the Port' (Yabele Media) <<https://yabelemedia.com/2025/09/03/7571/>> accessed on 23 November 2025

¹⁵⁹ Philip Noonan, 'Revolutions and Treaty Termination' (1984) 2(2) Penn International Law Review 301

¹⁶⁰ Elias N. Stebek, 'River Maiteb's Location in the Ethio-Eritrean Western Border: Critical Reflections' (2009) 3(1) Mizan Law Review 149

¹⁶¹ Algiers Agreement

¹⁶² Mehari Fissaha, 'The challenges of the United Nations Effort in the Furtherance of Peace and Security in the Horn of Africa: The Case of the Ethiopian- Eritrea Border' (2017)

¹⁶³ BBC, 'Ethiopia offers Eritrea chance to end Africa's longest war' accessed from <<https://www.bbc.com/news/world-africa-44381701>> accessed on 4 July 2025

demarcation pillars on the ground.¹⁶⁴ Owing to this, Ethiopia and Eritrea have only delimited boundaries without demarcated frontiers.¹⁶⁵

Accordingly, Dejen Yemane argued that Eritrean secession is incomplete state formation and he argued so long as the issue of Ethiopia's right over Assab is not addressed during the Algiers Agreement Ethiopia can assert its right at any time.¹⁶⁶ Similarly, Dr. Yacob argues that the decision of the EEBC is incomplete and calls another negotiation to realize Ethiopia's quest over Assab.¹⁶⁷ Unfortunately, during its dissolution the EEBC stated that 'until such time as the boundary is finally demarcated, the delimitation decision of 13 April 2002 continues as the only valid legal description of the boundary.'¹⁶⁸ Therefore, the ruling of the EEBC is continued to be used as a reference to demarcate the Ethio-Eritrea boundary dispute. Resultantly, arranging another boundary negotiation or instituting legal proceedings before international courts will hinder Ethiopia's claims of ownership over Assab.

During the negotiation process of the Algiers Agreement Ethiopia's right to access the sea was not the part contestation between Ethiopia and Eritrea.¹⁶⁹ Accordingly, some contend that Ethiopia has voluntarily renounced its historical and legitimate right over Assab and the coastal area of the Red Sea.¹⁷⁰ Unlike other commissions, the EEBC has never conducted physical observation and investigation on the disputed areas.¹⁷¹ Instead, the commission grants rush ruling by simply looking colonial treaties and maps which were prepared by Italy. However, colonial treaties and maps used by the commission are nullified by the repeated aggression act of Italy.¹⁷² Moreover, on 11 September 1952, Ethiopia declared the nullification of all colonial treaties (1900, 1902 and 1908)

¹⁶⁴ International Crisis Group, 'Beyond the Fragile Peace Between Ethiopia and Eritrea: Averting New War' <<https://www.crisisgroup.org/africa/horn-africa/eritrea/beyond-fragile-peace-between-ethiopia-and-eritrea-averting-new-war>> accessed on 25 July 2025

¹⁶⁵ Berita Mutinda Musau, Uti Possidetis, 'Self-determination and Conflicts in the Horn of Africa: The Case of Eritrea's Secession from and Border Conflict with Ethiopia' (2022) 8(2) *Journal of Conflict Management and Sustainable Development* 218

¹⁶⁶ Dejen Yemane, 'After Fumbling Assab, Meles Did Right by Nile' *Addis Fortune* (Addis Abeba, 21 March 2020) <<https://addisfortune.news/after-fumbling-assab-meles-did-right-by-nile/>> accessed on 5 September 2025

¹⁶⁷ Yacob Hailemariam

¹⁶⁸ Reuters, 'Ethiopia-Eritrea commission ends, border unresolved' accessed from <<https://www.reuters.com/article/economy/ethiopia-eritrea-commission-ends-border-unresolved-idUSL3048408/>>

¹⁶⁹ Eritrea-Ethiopia Claims Commission - Final Award, Ports Ethiopia's Claim 6 between The Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia and The State of Eritrea, The Hague, August 17, 2009

¹⁷⁰ Efreem Yemane, 'Reflections on an Aspect of the Boundary Commission's Decision: The Revision of Ethiopian History to Perpetuate past Colonialist Agenda' <https://www.ethiopians.com/Views/Efreem_YB_BorderRuling.htm> accessed on 22 August 2025

¹⁷¹ Sarbo Dima Noggo, 'The Eritrea-Ethiopia conflict: Domestic and regional ramifications and the role of the international community' (2013) *Global Economic Governance Programme Working Paper*, No. 2013/79

¹⁷² *Ibid*

concluded with Italy by adopting decree number 6/1952.¹⁷³ Appallingly, EPRDF agreed to resolve the Ethio-Eritrea boundary dispute based on colonial treaties and maps which favored Eritrea.

The immediate refusal of the finding of the commission by Ethiopia and the ending of the United Nation Peacekeeping Mission to Eritrea and Ethiopia by Eritrea deprived the compulsory nature of the Algiers Agreement and the ruling of EEBC.¹⁷⁴ Some may disregard this argument by contending that Ethiopia has expressed its willingness to accept the Algiers Agreement and the ruling of EEBC for several times. Indeed, on 7 June 2007 Ethiopia Permanent Mission to United Nation addressed Ethiopia's commitment to the unconditional acceptance of the ruling of EEBC on the letter issued to the President of the Security Council.¹⁷⁵ In 2016 EPRDF decided to fully accept and implement the finding of EEBC to normalize Ethio-Eritrea relations.¹⁷⁶

More recently, upon the coming in to power of Abiy Ahmed, on 5 June 2018 EPRDF Executive Committee issued an unprecedented statement it officially announces Ethiopia's acceptance of the Algiers Agreement and the ruling of EEBC without any reservation.¹⁷⁷ However, the subsequent acceptance of the Algiers Agreement and the ruling of EEBC were not ratified by Parliament; it was solely the decision of the ruling party, the EPRDF, or that of the executive organs of the government. In the Ethiopian legal system, international commitments create international obligations only when they are ratified by Parliament.¹⁷⁸ Accordingly, subsequent acceptance of the Algiers Agreement and the ruling of EEBC do not create any binding international obligations on Ethiopia.

e. Unilateral statement of Ethiopian authorities about Assab and international law

Unilateral declarations and statements made by competent authority create binding international obligations.¹⁷⁹ Unilateral statements create binding international law only

¹⁷³ Yonas Amare, 'የባህር ቦር ጉዳዮች እና አለም አቀፍ ህጎች [The issue of sea access and international laws]' The Ethiopian Reporter (Addis Abeba, 5 November 2023) <<https://www.ethiopianreporter.com/123742/>> accessed on 22 June 2025

¹⁷⁴ Yacob Hailemariam

¹⁷⁵ Lyons, Terrence, *The Ethiopia-Eritrea Conflict and the Search for Peace in the Horn of Africa* (2009) 36 *Review of African Political Economy* 167

¹⁷⁶ Awet T. Weldemichael, 'The specious dividends of peace in the Horn of Africa' (2021) 24(2) *Afriche Orienti* 57,

¹⁷⁷ EBC, 'የኢትዮ ኤርትራን የድንበር ግጭት ለመፍታት የተፈረመው የአልጀርስ ስምምነት ይዘት ምንድ ነው [what is the content of the Algiers Agreement that is signed to resolve Ethio-Eritrea boundary dispute]' accessed from <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vkwS4ELv_tY&list=PPSV>

¹⁷⁸ Abebew Sisay Alemnow, 'Legal effect of Unpublished International Law on Federal Negarit Gazttee under the Ethiopian Legal System' (2025) 2(1) *Chokie Journal of Law* 55

¹⁷⁹ Lina Subhi Hamdan, 'Unilateral Declarations of States: as a Potential Source of International Law' (LLM Thesis, Arab American University 2022)

when they are made officially by competent authority with the intention to bound.¹⁸⁰ Egypt's unilateral declaration deposited in the UN Secretary General, made in 1957 on Suez Canal to reaffirm the Constantinople Convention is recognized as a binding international legal document.¹⁸¹ In this statement Egypt expressed its willingness to allow free navigations for all states on the Suez Canal. In the Nuclear Tests cases (Australia v. France; New Zealand v. France) in 1974, the International Court of Justice (ICJ) ruled that unilateral declarations can create binding international obligations.¹⁸²

In this case, the court ruled that unilateral statements made by France authorities not to conduct nuclear tests in the atmosphere of the Pacific Ocean obliges France to refrain from testing atmospheric nuclear weapons in the Pacific Ocean.¹⁸³ To use unilateral declarations as a source of international law, ICJ prescribes intention to be bound and publicity as a precondition.¹⁸⁴ Therefore, when these preconditions are fulfilled, unilateral declaration creates binding international obligation without subsequent response or reaction from other states.¹⁸⁵ The decision of the court is formulated by the International Law Commission, in its guiding principles applicable to unilateral declarations of states capable of creating legal obligations in 2006.¹⁸⁶ As stated under this guiding principle, 'declarations publicly made and manifesting the will to be bound may have the effect of creating legal obligations.'¹⁸⁷

In his political orientation former Ethiopian Prime Minister, Meles Zenawi has officially stated that we are continuing to be bound by colonial treaties signed by emperor Menelik (1900, 1902 and 1908) hence international treaties are not terminated upon the change of government.¹⁸⁸ Beside this, he stated that 'some say that as we do not have a gateway to the sea, we have to use force and occupy it, but trying to take away a land that belongs to an internationally recognized country is terrorism in the eyes of international

¹⁸⁰ Tran Thikim Nguyen & Nguyen Mai Huong, 'The Validity of Unilateral Declarations on Maritime outer limits concerning Fundamental Changes due to Sea Level rise' (2024) 10(1) Vietnamese Journal of Legal Sciences 85

¹⁸¹ Sabel R, 'Freedom of Navigation through International Waterways in the Region: In International Law and the Arab-Israeli Conflict' (Cambridge University Press 2022) 333

¹⁸² Nuclear Test Cases (Australia v. France, New Zealand v. France), December 20, 1974. International Court of Justice' 1975 9(3) International Lawyer 563

¹⁸³ Nuclear Test Case(Australia vs France) 1974 ICJ Rep 22

¹⁸⁴ Ibid

¹⁸⁵ Benito Müller, Wouter Geldhof & Tom Ruys, 'Unilateral Declarations: The Missing Legal Link in the Bali Action Plan' (2010) European Capacity Building Initiative 1

¹⁸⁶ Víctor Rodríguez Cedeño & María Isabel Torres Cazorla, 'Unilateral Acts of States in International Law' Oxford Public International Law accessed from <<https://opil.ouplaw.com/display/10.1093/law:epil/9780199231690/law-9780199231690-e1496>>

¹⁸⁷ International Law Commission, Guiding Principles Applicable to Unilateral Declarations of States Capable of Creating Legal Obligations, with Commentaries thereto, 2006

¹⁸⁸ Red Sea Media Network, 'መለስ ዜናዊ ስለ አሱብ ጥያቄ የሰጠው ምላሽ (Meles Zenawi response about Assab)' accessed from <<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Ulh49g2a38>>

law.¹⁸⁹ Accordingly, Dereje Zeleke argued that the unilateral statement of the Prime Minister completely delegatized Ethiopia's claims of ownership over Assab.¹⁹⁰ However, in his speech Meles stated that 'until the situation in Eritrea becomes more favorable to us we have decided to leave this question for the future, however we are not saying we will not request to use the Assab port in the future by using international law.'¹⁹¹

Therefore, Melse addressed only temporary renouncement of Ethiopia's historical right until circumstances are propitious to assert Ethiopia's claim over Assab. Moreover, unilateral statements which are "political nature or orientation" cannot create binding international obligation. As a result, his statement does not create international obligation on Ethiopia. In several election campaigns several representatives of EPRDF disregarded the quest of opposition political parties over Assab, by contending that it violates Eritrean sovereignty.¹⁹² Unilateral declarations create binding international obligations only when it's made by a competent authority. Authorities who represent EPRDF in election campaigns are not competent to make statements about Ethiopia's quest over Assab.

In summary, Ethiopia lost its legitimate and historical rights over Assab due to the EPRDF's handling of the history *of the matter*. Undoubtedly, had the legal and historical arguments currently being invoked to legitimize Ethiopia's claim of ownership over Assab been raised during the Eritrean secession or the Algiers Agreement negotiations, Ethiopia would likely have retained the port. The EPRDF's unconditional recognition of Eritrea as an independent sovereign state, coupled with its unreserved acceptance of the Algiers Agreement and the subsequent EEBC ruling, has significantly undermined Ethiopia's contemporary aspirations regarding Assab. Furthermore, the EPRDF's erroneous characterization of the significance of maritime access effectively undermined Ethiopia's legal standing along the Red Sea coast, thereby weakening the modern legal and historical arguments now being utilized to advocate for adequate sea access.

Therefore, without considering the above mal historical acts of EPRDF which undermine contemporary Ethiopia's quest over Assab, the international community should perceive Ethiopia's quest in consideration of the way in which Ethiopia deprived its ownership over Assab and the significance of Ethiopia's presence in the Red Sea for regional stability.¹⁹³ Ethiopia is an artificially created landlocked state then, looking

¹⁸⁹ Teodros Brehan, 'Reflections on the political and legal alternatives for the restoration of Ethiopia's legitimate rights to the Assab region' <https://www.ethiopians.com/teodros_brehan_On_Assab.htm> accessed on July 21 2025

¹⁹⁰ Borkena, 'No way to make Assab part of Ethiopia,' says a legal scholar' accessed from <<https://borkena.com/2019/06/01/no-way-to-make-assab-part-of-ethiopia-says-a-legal-scholar/>> accessed on 8 November 2025

¹⁹¹ Horn Africa Insight, Djibouti's Silent Power: Ethiopia's Future Depends on This accessed from <<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5ta1CUod99Q>> accessed on 18 November 2025

¹⁹² Bereket100, Arkebe Oqbay during 2010 Elections <<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=nugG-3EGPDE>> accessed on 10 July 2025

¹⁹³ Gizachew Asrat & Gashaw Ayferam Endaylalu, Ethiopia's Quest for Sovereign Sea Access: Historical and Geopolitical Contexts (2025) 17 (1) Journal of Middle Eastern Studies 149

Ethiopia's quest in the same lenses with the quest of other landlocked states which are naturally landlocked is not equitable and rectitude.¹⁹⁴ Negotiating in good faith on international disputes is an internationally recognized principle of international law.¹⁹⁵ This principle is reaffirmed by the International Court of Justice.¹⁹⁶ Meanwhile, Eritrea has an international obligation to negotiate with Ethiopia in regard to its quest over Assab.

Eritrea should not contemplate Ethiopia's quest over Assab as a threat for its national interest and sovereignty. An Ethiopia claim of ownership over Assab is based on the principle of reciprocity and mutual economic benefit. Ethiopia offered several public enterprises including the Great Ethiopian Renaissance Dam for Eritrea in exchange for using Assab.¹⁹⁷ Ethiopia has several public enterprises which can generate a profit of billion dollars in a year. In regard to contemporary controversy over Assab between Ethiopia and Eritrea, this paper has formulated two permanent win-win solutions. First, establish joint sovereignty over Assab in exchange for Eritrea taking a share from Ethiopia's public enterprises. El Salvador, Honduras and Nicaragua have exercised a tripartite condominium over the Gulf of Fonseca.¹⁹⁸ Germany and Luxembourg have joint governmental authorities over the Moselle River.¹⁹⁹

Similarly, Ethiopia and Eritrea can deescalate their contestation and ensure mutual benefit by establishing joint sovereignty over Assab. Second, ratify the Asmera Declaration and Jeddah Peace Agreement which was signed in 2018 between Ethiopia and Eritrea. These agreements played a vital role in the rapprochement of the Ethio-Eritrea relation in 2018.²⁰⁰ In these agreements, the two states agreed to open the port of Assab and Massawa for Ethiopia. However, the agreement remained a gentlemen's agreement due to the unwillingness of Eritrea to ratify it.²⁰¹ Kenya reportedly expressed its willingness to provide secure access to the Indian Ocean for Uganda shortly after

¹⁹⁴ 'Historical Injustice: The Unjust Seizure of Assab Port And Ethiopia's Right To Reclaim Its Maritime Access'

Assab Forum (9 March 2025) < <https://www.assabforum.net/economic-impact-of-being-landlocked/> > accessed on 21 July 2025

¹⁹⁵ Andrew D Mitchell, 'Good Faith in WTO Dispute Settlement' (2006) 7 Melbourne Journal of International Law 340

¹⁹⁶ AFM Maniruzzaman, 'The Concept of Good Faith in the International Investment Dispute: The Arbitrators Dilemma' (2012) 89 The Journal of the Society for Advanced Legal Studies 16

¹⁹⁷ Fana Television

¹⁹⁸ Vivian Lezama Pizzati, History and Development: A condominium in the Gulf of Fonseca' United Nations – The Nippon Foundation of Japan Fellowship Program 2016

¹⁹⁹ Jeff Da Costa, Elizabeth Ebert and others, 'Signals Without Action: A Value Chain Analysis of Luxembourg's 2021 Flood Disaster' (2025) EGU Sphere Preprint <<https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-2025-3892>>

²⁰⁰ Aljazeera, 'Ethiopia, Eritrea sign peace deal at Saudi Arabia summit' accessed from <<https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2018/9/17/ethiopia-eritrea-sign-peace-deal-at-saudi-arabia-summit>>

²⁰¹ Tghat, 'Ethiopia's pursuit of ports: Ethio-Eritrea war pact| Eritrea's policy of self-sabotage' accessed from <<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6NEcSymGKvQ>>

President Museveni's assertion on the matter.²⁰² Ethiopia's repeated diplomatic overtures for negotiations concerning its urgent need for maritime access have been repudiated by the government of Eritrea, primarily due to the unyielding foreign policy of President Isaias Afwerki.

5. ETHIOPIA'S QUEST TO ACCESS THE RED SEA AND INTERNATIONAL LAW OF SEA

The 1982 United Nations Convention on the Law of Sea (UNCLOS) is the most comprehensive law of the sea that grants numerous rights to the landlocked states.²⁰³ As it's enshrined in the convention, landlocked states have the right of access to and from the sea, freedom of navigation, equal treatment in ports and so on.²⁰⁴ More importantly the convention incorporated the principle of 'common heritage of mankind' which precludes the exploitation of natural resource by coastal states alone.²⁰⁵ Therefore the convention allows land-locked states to utilize natural resources available on the sea. Invoking the UNCLOS is the most facile, legitimate and acceptable approach to realize Ethiopia's quest for access to the sea. The quest of land locked countries to access the sea is usually actualized under the auspices of the UNCLOS.

As enshrined in article 125 (1) of the UNCLOS landlocked states have the right to access the sea to enjoy rights guaranteed in the convention.²⁰⁶ It provides that;

Land-locked States shall have the right of access to and from the sea for the purpose of exercising the rights provided for in this Convention including those relating to the freedom of the high seas and the common heritage of mankind. To this end, land-locked States shall enjoy freedom of transit through the territory of transit States by all means of transport.²⁰⁷

Based on this provision, there is for and against argument among legal scholars on the way land locked states can access the sea. Some contend that UNCLOS absolutely grants

²⁰² Luke Anami 'Kenya assures Museveni as demands for sea access grow louder in East Africa' *The East African*(Nairobi, 13 November, 2025) <https://www.theeastafrican.co.ke/tea/news/east-africa/kenya-assures-museveni-as-demands-for-sea-access-grow-louder-5262962#google_vignette> accessed on 25 November 2025

²⁰³ Kishor Uprety, 'From Barcelona to Montego Bay and Thereafter: A Search for Landlocked States' "Rights to Trade through Access to the Sea A Retrospective Review' (2003) 7 *Singapore Journal of International & Comparative Law* 201

²⁰⁴ A.A Adedeji, 'An appraisal of the right of access to the sea accorded to landlocked states under the 1982 third United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCOLS)' (2007) 1(1) *Jimma University Journal of Law* 133

²⁰⁵ Imad Karrit, 'Rethinking the limitations in the enforceability of freedom of transit in the context of the Mozambican gas industry under Article V of the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade' (LLM Thesis, University of Pretoria, 2016)

²⁰⁶ Nigatu Kochito, 'Ethiopia's Landlockedness and its Implications for National security: Challenges and prospects' (MA Thesis, Ethiopian Civil Service University 2025)

²⁰⁷ United Nation Convention on the Law of the Sea 1982, UNTS 397, 21 ILM 1261

landlocked countries access to the sea and impose an obligation on the coastal state to provide sea access for land-locked states.²⁰⁸ While, other legal scholars argue that UNCLOS affords the right to access sea and transition to landlocked countries only when these States can enter into binding bilateral or multilateral agreements with coastal states. Apart from the above two arguments, Lauterpacht contended that so long as states proved that accessing the sea is a matter of necessity and exercising such right is not prejudice to the coastal states, landlocked states can access the sea.²⁰⁹ Ethiopia perceives its quest for access to the sea as a matter of existence.²¹⁰ Some argued that the large population and burgeoning economic growth of Ethiopia legitimize its quest to access the sea.²¹¹

The position taken by this paper is that UNCLOS grants right of access to the sea for landlocked states based on arrangements made with the coastal states.²¹² Hence, as it's envisaged in article 125(2) of the convention; 'the terms and modalities for exercising freedom of transit shall be agreed between the land-locked States and transit States concerned through bilateral, sub regional or regional agreements.'²¹³ When we construe this provision literally, we may contend that, the convention requires the agreement between the States only on the 'term and modalities of exercising the freedom of transit.'²¹⁴ Accordingly, some may argue that bilateral or regional agreements are not an automatic prerequisite to exercise the rights bestowed under the convention. However, how landlocked states can enjoy rights entitled under the convention without reaching agreement on the "terms and modalities" of exercising rights with coastal states.

In other words, what would be if the coastal States are unwilling to enter into binding bilateral or multilateral agreement on the terms and modalities of exercising right under the convention with landlocked states? Accordingly, the author argued that the UNCLOS grants the right to access sea and transition to landlocked countries only when these States can enter into binding bilateral or multilateral agreements with coastal states.²¹⁵ However, applying a uniform interpretation of this article to both naturally landlocked and artificially landlocked states contradicts the principles of fairness and equity, which have attained the status of customary international law. Accordingly, this

²⁰⁸ Naresh Giri, 'Nepal's Transit Route Negotiation with India and China' (2023) 3(1) *Journal of Foreign Affairs* 74

²⁰⁹ A. Mpazi Sinjela, 'Freedom of Transit and the Right of Access for Land-Locked States: The Evolution of Principle and Law' (1982) 12(1) *Global Journal of International Law and Comparative Law* 31

²¹⁰ 'The Basis of Ethiopia's Right to the Sea and International Law in Regaining Its Rights to Assab Port' *Assab Forum* (30 March 2025) <<https://www.assabforum.net/the-basis-of-ethiopias-right-to-the-sea-and-international-law-in-regaining-its-rights-to-assab-port/>> accessed on 21 July 2025

²¹¹ EBC, 'Elevating Sea Access from a Suppressed Subject to a National Agenda' accessed from <<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=K5B3tl3v6NM&t=13s>> accessed on 14 November 2025

²¹² Bojotlhe O. G. Butale, 'Bridging the gap to the sea for Landlocked states: A case for Botswana' (2016) *United Nations -The Nippon Foundation of Japan Fellowship Programme*

²¹³ *Id.*, 168

²¹⁴ Ramesh Kumar, 'Right of access of land-locked state to the sea by the example of bilateral agreement between land-locked state Nepal and port state India' (LLM Thesis, University of Tromso 2010)

²¹⁵ Nancy Napol, 'The Rights of African Landlocked States under the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea: Real or illusory rights?' (LLM Thesis, Cape Town University 2021)

paper contends that that Article 125 of UNCLOS should be interpreted in light of the specific circumstances under which a state loses its maritime frontage. In cases where a state is deprived of sea access through political conspiracy such as the specific arrangements between the TPLF and the EPLF international law should impose a positive obligation on coastal states to negotiate. Under this view, because Ethiopia's landlocked status resulted from irresponsible political acts rather than a legitimate, equitable process of state succession, the right of access should be treated as a remedial right rather than a mere transit privilege.

Some authorities utilize the ruling of the International Court of Justice in the *Bolivia v. Chile* case to consolidate the argument that landlocked states can only access the sea through arrangements made with coastal states.²¹⁶ Bolivia has deprived its access to the Pacific Ocean due to the annexation of the port of Antofagasta by Chile and the Treaty of Peace and Friendship in 1879 and 1904 respectively.²¹⁷ In 2013, Bolivia instituted proceedings against Chile before the International Court of Justice, basing its claims on unilateral statements and diplomatic negotiations contending that contends that "Chile has an obligation to negotiate an agreement granting Bolivia sovereign access to the Pacific Ocean."²¹⁸

However, the ICJ rejected Bolivia's claim by deciding that Chile has no obligation to negotiate with Chile to provide secure sea access in the Pacific Ocean.²¹⁹ Notably, Bolivia did not invoke Article 125 of the UNCLOS as a legal basis for its arguments.²²⁰ Consequently, the ICJ did not interpret that specific provision. Since the ICJ did not interpret Article 125 of UNCLOS in its judgment, the ruling cannot serve as an authoritative source for interpreting that provision. The Courts analysis focused exclusively on the legal implications of unilateral acts and diplomatic negotiations, leaving it without the jurisprudential mandate to define or qualify the transit rights codified in the treaty. Consequently, because the Court never addressed the merits of Article 125, the decision cannot be invoked as a precedent to limit the statutory rights of landlocked states under UNCLOS.

²¹⁶ Filmon Yemane, 'A Persistent Threat: International Law and Ethiopia's New Maritime Ambitions' <<https://setit.org/a-persistent-threat-international-law-and-ethiopia-s-new-maritime-ambitions/>> accessed on 21 December 2025

²¹⁷ Application Instituting Proceedings on the Obligation to Negotiate Access to the Pacific Ocean (*Bolivia v. Chile*), 2013 I.C.J. No. 153, (Apr. 24, 2013)

²¹⁸ Zach J. Kleiman, 'The Long, Not-So Pacific Struggle for the Coast: A Border Dispute between Chile and Bolivia' (2016) 22(3) *Law and Business of Review of the Americas* 247

²¹⁹ Diane Desierto, 'Beyond Good Neighborliness in the ICJ 1 October 2018 Judgment in *Bolivia v. Chile*: Do Human Rights and Sustainable Development Obligate Creating Negotiated Access for Landlocked Bolivia to the Pacific Ocean' <<https://www.ejiltalk.org/beyond-the-icj-1-october-2018-judgment-in-bolivia-v-chile-do-human-rights-obligate-negotiated-access-to-the-pacific-ocean/>>

²²⁰ Christopher R. Rossi, 'A Case Ill Suited for Judgment: Constructing 'A Sovereign Access to the Sea' in the Atacama Desert' (2017) 48(2) *University of Miami Inter-American Law Review* 28

The rights of landlocked countries embedded in the convention are not “self-executing” and absolute.²²¹ Indeed the convention imposed an obligation on coastal states to ‘fulfill in good faith the obligations assumed under the convention.’²²² Moreover, coastal states cannot invoke sovereignty to exonerate from obligations recognized in the convention.²²³ Therefore, although coastal states are not obliged to reach agreement with landlocked states, they are compelled to act in good faith.

Some scholars contend that the finding of the ICJ in the Bolivia vs Chile case challenges the legitimacy of Ethiopia’s ongoing quest.²²⁴ However, the legal foundations of the two cases are fundamentally distinct. While Bolivia relied on the doctrine of unilateral acts contending that past diplomatic exchanges created a binding obligation to negotiate Ethiopia’s position is predicated on the legal invalidity of the historical and political processes that rendered it landlocked. To enjoy rights entitled under the convention states are required to deposit their instrument of ratification before the Secretary General of the United Nation.²²⁵ Ethiopia signed the UNCLOS in 1982 and ratified it in 2012.²²⁶

However, Ethiopia failed to deposit the instrument of ratification proclamation before the Secretary General of the United Nations. Accordingly, some authors contend that Ethiopia cannot invoke the UNCLOS to legitimize its ongoing quest to access the sea; hence Ethiopia is not a party to the convention.²²⁷ Moreover, some authors argued that during the negotiation process of the convention, Group 77 countries including Ethiopia agreed that states which are not the party to the convention cannot invoke the convention to enjoy rights bestowed in the UNCLOS.²²⁸

However, this paper is of the view that failure to deposit the instrument of ratification and the common intention of Group 77 cannot preclude Ethiopia from invoking the

²²¹ Dagnachew Tesfaye, ‘Convention and Statute Serving Landlocked Developing States: the Case of Ethiopia’ <<https://dmethiolawyers.com/convention-and-statute-serving-landlocked-developing-states-the-case-of-ethiopia/>> accessed on 2 June 2025

²²² See article 300 of the convention

²²³ See article 2(3) of the convention

²²⁴ Angelina Shchukina, ‘Ethiopia’s Negotiations on Access to the Sea: Can International Law Help Find a Solution?’ European Journal of International Law Blog <<https://www.ejiltalk.org/ethiopias-negotiations-on-access-to-the-sea-can-international-law-help-find-a-solution/>> accessed on 21 December 2025; Filmon Yemane, ‘A Persistent Threat: International Law and Ethiopia’s New Maritime Ambitions’ <<https://setit.org/a-persistent-threat-international-law-and-ethiopias-new-maritime-ambitions/>> accessed on 21 December 2025

²²⁵ Peter Malanczuk, Akehurts Modern Introduction to International Law (Routledge, 7th ed 1997)

²²⁶ ‘Ethiopia’s Right to the Sea Under International Law’ The Reporter (Addis Abeba, 8 March 2025) <<https://www.thereporterethiopia.com/44075/>> accessed on 25 June 2025

²²⁷ Jara Samuel, ‘Red Sea Dreams: Ethiopia’s Challenges and Hopes Amid International Law and Geopolitics’ (African Legal Studies Blog, 2 May 2025) <<https://africanlegalstudies.blog/2025/05/02/red-sea-dreams-ethiopias-challenges-and-hopes-amid-international-law-and-geopolitics/>> accessed on 25 June 2025

²²⁸ Angelina Shchukina, ‘Ethiopia’s Negotiations on Access to the Sea: Can International Law Help Find a Solution’ <<https://www.ejiltalk.org/ethiopias-negotiations-on-access-to-the-sea-can-international-law-help-find-a-solution/>> accessed on 23 June 2025

Convention to legitimize its ambition to access the sea. Hence, firstly ratification is one of the ways by which States express their consent to be bound by bilateral and multilateral treaties.²²⁹ Therefore, Ethiopia has expressed its intention to be bound by the UNCLOS via participating in the negotiation process with full power of representation and ratification of the convention. Secondly, UNCLOS provides a geographical definition for landlocked states without a consideration to the states as a party to the convention. The convention defines landlocked States as ‘States which have no sea coast.’²³⁰ Furthermore, unlike the 1965 Convention on Transit Trade of Land-locked States, the convention deliberately employs the phrase “landlocked States” instead of “contracting parties” in all its provisions.

Consequently, according to the cumulative reading of those facts with article 125 of the convention, we can argue that the convention provides all rights entitled for landlocked states irrespective of their status to the convention. Thirdly, several provisions of the UNCLOS attain customary international law status.²³¹ The ICJ recognized that several provisions of UNCLOS have attained customary international law status. Specifically, in its judgment on the Maritime Delimitation and Territorial Questions between Qatar and Bahrain the court ruled that article 121(2) of the convention reached customary international law status.²³² Similarly, in the case between Nicaragua vs Colombia the court found that rights and obligations embedded under article 56, 58, 61, 62 and 73 of the UNCLOS qualify for customary international law status.²³³ Therefore, so long as the coastal states are not persistent objector of the UNCLOS, non-member states of the convention are bound by the UNCLOS. Similarly, Ethiopia can invoke the convention to enjoy rights entitled in the conventions to landlocked states.

With regards to Eritrea, some authors argue that so long as Eritrea does not sign and ratify UNCLOS, Ethiopia cannot invoke the convention to legitimize its quest to access the sea via Eritrea.²³⁴ However, the right of landlocked countries to access sea and transition attains customary international law status, then Ethiopia can invoke the convention to retort its quest of access to the sea notwithstanding Eritrea does not sign

²²⁹ Muhammad Afzal & Shahzada Aamir Mushtaq, ‘The Concept of Ratification of Treaties and Protocols in Public International Law and Their Non-Binding Effects on Developing Countries’ Sovereignty: A Case Study of Pakistan’ (2024) 5(3) *Annals of Human and Social Sciences* 546

²³⁰ See article 124 of the convention

²³¹ Martin Lishexian Lee, ‘The Interrelation Between the Law of the Sea Convention and Customary International

Law’ (2006) 7 *San Diego International Law Journal* 405; Cezary Mik, ‘Custom in the Present International Law of Sea’ (2018) 8(2) *Wroclaw Review of Law, Administration & Economics* 127

²³² Amos O. Enabulele, Customary International Law through Treaty Consensus 2023 2(1) *Journal of Community & International Law* 47

²³³ Question of the Delimitation of the Continental Shelf between Nicaragua and Colombia beyond 200 Nautical Miles from the Nicaraguan Coast (Nicaragua v. Colombia) 2023 ICJ Rep 3

²³⁴ Mahemud Eshetu Tekuya, ‘Essay Swimming against the current: Ethiopia’s quest for access to the Red sea under International Law’ (2024) 47(3) *Fordham International Law Journal* 302

the convention.²³⁵ Hence, Eritrea is not a persistent objector of the convention and consequently has an obligation to abide by the rules and principles of the UNCLOS which attains customary international law status. Due to the geopolitical strategic significance of the Red Sea Ethiopia's demand to access the sea has not only legal impediment. Egypt and Eritrea saw Ethiopia's presence in the Red Sea as a threat to their national interest and security.²³⁶ That is why Egypt and Eritrea release several joint statements by stating that States which are not geographically connected with the Red Sea have no legitimate right to access Red Sea.²³⁷

Ethiopia has proposed an equity-for-access model, offering stakes in major state-owned enterprises such as Ethiopian Airlines, Ethio-Telecom, and the Grand Ethiopian Renaissance Dam to coastal states in exchange for a sovereign sea outlet.²³⁸ Consequently, neighboring coastal states should not view Ethiopia's pursuit of maritime access as a threat to their national interests or security. On the contrary, granting Ethiopia access to the sea offers significant economic, political, and social benefits to the Horn of Africa region.²³⁹ Economically, such an arrangement enables coastal states to generate revenue through port leases, foster bilateral trade, and ensure secure maritime commerce by collectively combating piracy. Politically, a permanent Ethiopian presence in the Red Sea is vital for regional stability, particularly in preventing and suppressing terrorism and violent extremism. Socially, this cooperation facilitates the management of irregular migration, smuggling, and human trafficking, while strengthening transboundary cultural ties, linguistic exchange, and religious connections.

Ethiopia's ongoing quest for maritime access extends beyond the mere procurement of port services. Instead, Ethiopia is asserting claims of ownership over coastal regions of the Red Sea by invoking legal, historical, and demographic justifications under the auspices of UNCLOS. However, UNCLOS does not grant landlocked states sovereign ownership over any portion of the maritime territory of coastal states. The author of this article contends that Ethiopia's pursuit of maritime access should be decoupled from claims of territorial ownership over coastal areas, with the potential exception of Assab. Persistent claims of sovereignty exacerbate tensions, thereby

²³⁵ Kishor Uprety, *The Transit Regime for Landlocked States: International Law and Development Perspectives*

[2006] World Bank Law, Justice and Development Series 1, 150

²³⁶ Horn Africa Insight, 'Egypt and Ethiopia Face off over Red Sea: New Tensions Across the Horn' accessed from <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=OZHcL-w_H4Y> accessed on 4 November 2025

²³⁷ 'Egyptian, Eritrean FMs reject involvement of non-bordering countries[Ethiopia] in Red Sea security' Ethio Review News <<https://ethioreview.org/2025/03/egyptian-eritrean-fms-reject-involvement-of-non-bordering-countriesethiopia-in-red-sea-security/>> accessed on 4 November 2025

²³⁸ Feature: A population of 150 million can't live in a geographic prison-PM Abiy Ahmed' Addis Standard (Addis Abeba, 14 October 2023) <<https://addisstandard.com/feature-a-population-of-150-million-cant-live-in-a-geographic-prison-pm-abiy-ahmed/>> accessed on 23 June 2025

²³⁹ Tsegaye Degineh, 'Between Liberalization and Geopolitics: Ethiopia's Quest for Economic Stability, Sea Access' The Reporter (Addis Abeba, 21 June 2025) <<https://www.thereporterethiopia.com/45720/>> accessed on 23 June 2025

undermining the diplomatic avenues through which Ethiopia might otherwise secure reliable maritime access. In contrast, the model established by Nepal and India serves as a functional alternative; the two nations have signed various transit agreements that facilitate Nepal's access to international markets, operating effectively under the framework of UNCLOS.²⁴⁰ Nepal uses the ports of Kolkata, Haldia, and Visakhapatnam to facilitate its import and export at cheap expense.²⁴¹ In their transit agreements two states have agreed to consult all matters which are a threat for their national security and interest.²⁴²

Similarly, Ethiopia can secure maritime access through bilateral negotiations with neighboring coastal states, predicated on the principle of reciprocity and in accordance with international law. With the exception of South Sudan, all of Ethiopia's neighbors possess coastlines, providing a strategic opportunity for Ethiopia to pursue transit rights in multiple directions. However, Ethiopia's current maritime ambitions are not confined to securing ports for commercial transit alone; national security and maritime defense are primary drivers of this pursuit. Given the region's strategic significance, establishing a permanent naval presence or a military base on the Red Sea involves far more complex legal and political considerations than merely procuring commercial port services.

Since coastal states particularly Eritrea, perceive Ethiopia's quest as a potential infringement upon their territorial integrity and sovereignty, the realization of Ethiopia's ambitions faces significant diplomatic hurdles. Consequently, before seeking to establish a military base, Ethiopia must foster strategic alliances and provide security guarantees to coastal states to mitigate regional tensions. Furthermore, the intensification of great power competition among global and emerging regional actors in the Horn of Africa will likely complicate Ethiopia's pursuit of maritime access in the Red Sea. Consequently, to realize its objective of securing sea access, Ethiopia must enhance its continental and international standing by engaging in efficacious diplomacy with these key stakeholders.

6. CONCLUSION

Although the significance of sea access is not debatable and questionable, Ethiopia's quest to access the sea should be addressed only in a way that will not undermine the sovereignty and territorial integrity of coastal states. Unless, attempt to get direct access to the sea affront to the sovereignty of coastal states will jeopardize Ethiopia's ongoing demand to access the sea. Hence, coastal states may perceive Ethiopia as imperialist and they fear that Ethiopia has an ambition to restore its entire former lost province by

²⁴⁰ Saroj Kumar Timalina, Trade and Transit Relations between Nepal and India: Political Implications (2023) 14(1) *Journal of Economic Concern* 84

²⁴¹ Pohit Sanjib, Overview of India-Nepal Trade: Trends, Trade Logistics and Impediments (2009) Munich Personal RePEc Archive, Paper No. 45874

²⁴² Lubina Sarwar, Indian-Nepal Relationship: An Analysis of Various Treaties International (2018) 6(1) *Journal of Research in Management & Social Science* 109

colonial powers to establish the ancient Abyssinian Empire.²⁴³ Neighboring coastal states should not consider Ethiopia's quest to access the sea as a threat to their national security. Ethiopia's presence in the Red Sea is vital to redress political and military concerns in the region of the horn.

To ensure perpetual and sustainable utilization over the coastal area of the Red Sea, the strategic significance of the Red Sea and the presence of great powers competition in the horn of Africa oblige Ethiopia to conduct efficacious and meticulous diplomacy and cooperation with neighboring coastal states under the umbrella of reciprocity.²⁴⁴ From the perspective of international law, although the economic and strategic importance of Assab is more significant than Berbera recognizing Somaliland in exchange for a maritime access seems much more legal than claiming ownership over Assab. Hence, as stated by Dereje Zeleke, irresponsible historical acts of EPRDF challenges the legality of Ethiopia's claims of ownership over Assab. However, the international community should perceive Ethiopia's quest to access the sea in consideration of the way in which Ethiopia deprived its presence over the coastal area of the Red Sea. Moreover, although the Algiers Agreement has revived the legality of colonial treaties, Ethiopia's immediate refusal of the finding of EEBC and non-ratification of subsequent acceptance of the Algiers Agreement exonerated Ethiopia from abided by the agreement.

International law of sea allows for landlocked countries to access the sea. However, to enjoy these rights, landlocked states should enter into an arrangement with coastal states. Therefore, to realize its quest to access the sea, Ethiopia should adopt effective foreign policy that encourages the coastal state to negotiate with it. The United Nations Charter imposed an obligation on states to solve disputes through negotiation and mediation. Accordingly, instead of equipping firearms for rebel forces based in Ethiopia, Eritrea should demonstrate its consent to negotiate with Ethiopia. Ethiopia repeatedly expressed its willingness to negotiate with coastal states particularly with Eritrea regarding its quest to access the Red Sea. Ethiopian Prime Minister Abiy Ahmed calls the international community to negotiate Ethiopia with Eritrea. However, the international community remained silent to arrange diplomatic discourse between Ethiopia and Eritrea. Regional, continental and international organizations like IGAD, EU, AU, UN and super powers should exert diplomatic leverage on Eritrea to negotiate with Ethiopia. Finally, the author recommends Ethiopia to deposit the instrument of ratification of the UNCLOS before the Secretary-General of the United Nations. Hence, it disregards the argument that Ethiopia is not the full member of the convention.

²⁴³Adnan Hashem, 'Looming War in the Horn of Africa: Ethiopia's quest for access to the Red Sea' (2024) Abaad Studies & Research Center

²⁴⁴Yirga Abebe, 'Contemporary Geopolitical Dynamics in the Horn of Africa: Challenge and Prospects for Ethiopia' (2021) 9(9) International Relation and Diplomacy 361